

SAMARITANEN

BEN-HAYYIM, Z. — A Grammar of Samaritan Hebrew. The Magnes Press, Jerusalem, 2000. (24 cm, XVIII, 491). ISBN 1-57506-047-7. \$40.00

This book is a translation, with slight revisions and corrections by the author, of the well-known grammar of Samaritan Hebrew published in 1977 as vol. V of the monumental work ʿBRYT WʿRMYT NWSH. *ShWMRWN* [English title-pages: *The Literary and Oral Tradition of Hebrew and Aramaic amongst the Samaritans*], commonly cited in Hebrew publications as ʿWʿNSh and in English publications as *LOT*. The original volume lying behind this translation is entitled LShWN TWRH *Leshon Torah* [English title-page: *Grammar of the Pentateuch*]. The five volumes (in six parts) of the set appeared between 1957 and 1977, and revolutionised the study of Samaritan Hebrew and Samaritan Aramaic, specially the latter; though it needs to be borne in mind that over this period much useful and in fact indispensable work was published by other scholars, notably Rudolf Macuch, and also that Ben-H.ayyim built on several centuries of European and Samaritan endeavour.

The translation under discussion here appeared just before the author turned 93, and the author was still working on the revision of the Hebrew original till after turning 91. I am informed indirectly from several sources that the author regarded this English translation as his last publication. It will be seen that the main editor's responsibility went beyond what would normally be required, and in fact the main editor's name — Abraham Tal — appears *on the title-page underneath the author's name*. It causes me considerable regret to say that the editors have not done their job. The book swarms with errors, some minor, but many quite serious. Over and over, I found myself turning to the Hebrew original to sort out a sentence that was either unintelligible or manifestly false. In view of the seriousness of the confusion that will be caused by this publication, I have taken this review beyond the normal length, so as to demonstrate beyond doubt that it needs to be re-done.

A word needs to be said about the ostensible purpose of this English translation. The preface says it is intended for “research or teaching purposes” by “scholars of Biblical Hebrew and Semitists” [sic], who would not be able to handle the Hebrew original. This justification does not stand up to examination. A person unable to handle the Hebrew original would derive minimal benefit from a grammar of Samaritan Hebrew, because they would have no context to put the information into. They would certainly not be in a position to teach historical Hebrew linguistics. Research in the field would be impossible. The author says (p. xiv top) that he thought it necessary to point the Hebrew words (he means words and phrases from Biblical Hebrew in the Tiberian Masoretic tradition). Can it be seriously suggested that a person unable to handle unpointed Masoretic Hebrew could do research in the field of Hebrew linguistics? It can be granted that a few scholars whose main interest is somewhere else in Semitic linguistics might be interested, but even then, the standard comparative handbooks would be more accessible and more useful. One can assess the intended market of this book as being the libraries of North American theological colleges. Certainly the price in U.S. currency is low enough for the book to be sold widely. To be cynical, perhaps the

inaccuracy of the book will not be noticed, and it will keep on being cited.

We will start with the section on the signs devised by the Samaritans themselves to mark the vowels, or to mark the doubling of consonants, and so on, paragraphs 0.7 and 0.8. In this section *the editors have actually introduced errors*. Furthermore, the author himself contributes to the reader's difficulty by leaving unaltered several references to information in another volume of the longer Hebrew set of volumes without quoting the necessary information. If the author was unable to correct this deficit, then the responsibility lies with the other person whose name is on the title-page. If the reader would like to read the section right through, it will be seen that *there is an overall obscurity that gives the impression that no-one has taken final responsibility for the final text to be printed*.

Here are the details, simplified as much as possible.

The section on the systems (more than one) used by the Samaritans to mark the vowels and other phonetic information is unnecessarily difficult even in the original Hebrew. *The signs are nowhere set out systematically in relation to their function*. There is a bare listing, with each sign being given a number, and then the reader has to try to annotate the list by reading the pages that follow (more than once, in my case at least) and by looking up an Arabic text, with the author's Hebrew translation, in another volume in this series or set. (The Hebrew translation does not clarify the argument enough to remove the need to read the Arabic original). To some extent, this fault in the organisation of the material was excusable in the original, which combined the presentation with a weighing-up of the evidence, but it is not excusable in a revised volume, specially one that will be bought and used on its own. *For three symbols, no phonetic value is given anywhere in this volume of the Hebrew original*, not in tabular form and not in the discussion. Instead, three Arabic words are cited as the names, and the reader then has to look up yet another volume in this set to find out the use of these names. i.e. a full competence in Hebrew and access to the original set and some knowledge of Arabic is demanded of the reader of a translation of this single volume! The first difficulty is to work out just where in the Samaritan Arabic treatises mentioned without any section or page reference the information about these three signs might be found. At the start of the first treatise three Hebrew words are listed as containing three sounds that need to be distinguished. The three Hebrew words correspond to three Arabic words, the same as quoted by Ben-H.ayyim in the paragraphs under discussion here. If Ben-H.ayyim's footnotes are then read, the first two vowels can be identified and the third can be guessed from the context. After that, the reader can shut this volume, go back to the grammar volume, and enter the three phonetic symbols in the margin or between the lines. Only then will the reader be able to identify the vowels termed "the brotherhood fath." or "the indication fath." or "the vocative fath." when they occur in other parts of the grammar volume. This is hard enough. What is the reader of the English translation going to make of the terms without access to the definitions? Actually, the reader is not even told what fath. means in Arabic. Yet the three terms are used — in English translation of the Arabic terms — in the translated volume in many places with no help given, e.g. in par. 1.2.7.1 "the brotherhood fath." is mentioned without any phonetic symbol.

Furthermore, *the editors have introduced a set of errors into the list of vowel-signs*. The list is correct in the Hebrew original. In a new note written for the English translation, Ben-H.ayyim refers to an article in Spanish by another scholar which discusses the multiple use of one of the signs. This article appeared in the published proceedings of a conference of the Société d'Etudes Samaritaines, with an addendum in English summarising Ben-H.ayyim's view of the new material presented. In this summary, as in the preceding article in Spanish, the sign is printed, but it is also identified by its number in Ben-H.ayyim's listing. The editors of this note in the conference volume, A.D. Crown and L. Davey, have allowed the correct number to stand, but have put in the wrong vowel-sign, even though there can be no doubt as to which sign is discussed in the preceding article. The editors Crown and Davey have done this, it seems, after looking up Ben-H.ayyim's listing in the Hebrew original of this book and reading the list from *left to right!* Keeping the correct number, the editors of this note have replaced the correct sign, which follows the figure and is on the left in a Hebrew book, by the sign to the right of the figure! Then, the editor of the book being reviewed here has looked up the article mentioned by Ben-H.ayyim, but instead of looking at the Spanish article, has looked at the following note in English, and has identified the figure with the wrong symbol. Ben-H.ayyim's words in this note in the conference volume can only refer to one particular symbol, so that the error is self-evident. The editor of the English translation of the grammar has noticed the discrepancy, but *has not used the preceding article (in Spanish) to correct it*, with the result that Ben-H.ayyim's numbering of the sign in the new note in the book being reviewed here has been changed, and the wrong vowel has been put in eighth place in the listing. As this sign should have been in seventh place, a partial pseudo-correction has then removed the vowel-sign in seventh place, *leaving a blank that could have been picked up even by a proofreader with no knowledge of the subject*. The sign that should have been in eighth place is omitted from the listing altogether! As a result of these errors, other errors occur in what follows, notably at the start of 0.8, and in the same section, p.8, line 5, where in both cases the wrong vowel is specified.

Alerted by what had gone wrong in this section as a result of active editorial interference and lack of due care, I went through the book looking out for sentences that were either meaningless or obviously wrong, and checking them against the original.

We will start with a few instances of straight miscopying. In par. 2.12.9, for P^cL with qamets and patah., read the same letters with patah. and qamets. The editor should have noticed that this paragraph is in the chapter on nouns, not the one on verbs. In 1.1.6.n.22, the free-standing letter *t* (in italics) should have been underlined (to represent an inter-dental fricative). In 1.4.4, p.66, line 11, the last letter of *iyi* (in italics) should have a macron, and in line 12, *iyim* (in italics, correctly with a macron over the second vowel) should have been written with the first consonant doubled. In 1.2.7.2, n.62, the *e* (in italics) followed by a comma should have been *e* (in italics) with a hook underneath. Substitution of *a* with a macron for *a* with a circle over it, or *a* with no modifier for *a* with a circle over it, or *e* for the I.P.A. *sheva* symbol (an upside-down *e*) and various similar errors, occur *too often to try to list*. The discussion of the distinction between three of the vowels at the top of p.50 has been made useless by the

omission of two diacritical marks, one for openness and another for length, on the first vowel of the first example. *Many more instances of wrong vowel-symbols could be added.*

Quite often errors have been introduced not by simple mis-copying or mistyping, but by pseudo-corrections at some editorial level that could only be due to failure to read and understand the argument. See p.190, middle, lines 20 and 22, where the distinction between forms with *u* and forms with *e* has been wiped out by a pseudo-correction. See also p.210, line 21. See also the first instance in the previous paragraph. This list could be greatly extended.

The errors in copying the illustrations from Babylonian Masoretic Hebrew, very frequently in the pointing but sometimes extending to the letters as well, are too numerous to list. Technical faults add to the obscurity. The font used for Babylonian vowel signs in the footnotes is too small to show up clearly on the coarse paper used. When the Babylonian vocalisation symbol is a superscript miniature Hebrew letter the result is a blob that will only be identifiable if the reader is very familiar with the subject, and sometimes not even then. Also, the font used for Babylonian vowel signs is not well shaped, and it is noticeable that the difficulty the reader has in distinguishing the signs has been the cause of a lot of the printing errors, specially the constant confusion between patah. and qamets. It might reasonably have been expected that the editors would have noticed the errors on the basis of some familiarity with the phonetics of Babylonian Hebrew.

Wrong references occur a few times, e.g. in 2.6.12, n.77, *sometimes even when referring to other volumes by the same author in this set*, e.g. in 1.2.6 at the start.

Instances of mistranslation abound. The following is only a sampling. In 1.1.3, n.7, the note on the Leiden ms. has been misunderstood. In 1.1.8.3, end, for “a distinction between verbs and nouns” read “a distinction between some verbs and some nouns”. The author means between verbs and nouns, and between nouns and nouns. In 1.2.1a, for “appears for *waw conjunctive* in a phrase such as...” read “appears for *waw conjunctive* in a phonetic grouping such as...”. In 1.2.6, start, for “expressed by *e*” read “realised as *e*”. In 1.3.1, n.69, for “the present discussion” read “his discussion”; and for “proofs brought” read “evidence cited”. In 1.3.5, start, confusion of tenses makes it impossible to follow the argument. In the same paragraph, for “can be accounted for only by means of the contact between the guttural consonant and the one following it, with no interference from forms such as...”, read “can be accounted for only on the basis of [direct] contact between the guttural consonant and the one following, without any hiatus of the type seen in forms such as...”. In the same paragraph, end, for “this patah. is found” read “this patah. is common”, and put the following word “after” in italics for contrastive emphasis, corresponding to letter-spacing in the original. In 1.4.1, start, replace “open” and “closed” by “simple” and “compound”. Same par., end, before “the vowel is not a short one”, insert “from the phonemic aspect”. In 1.4.3 we find “In this case there was no morphological aspect to geminate, but rather a mere phonetic one”. This is nonsense. How do you geminate an aspect? Read rather “In this case there is no morphological significance to the gemination, which in its origin is merely phonetically conditioned”. In 1.4.4, end, for “results in the splitting of the diphthong” read “results from the splitting of a diphthong”. In 1.4.5, end, for “as opposed to” read

“rather than”, since the forms cited after these words don’t occur, and the argument depends on this fact, as the editor should have understood. In 1.4.6, start, for “It is probable that this, too, is the stipulation for groups (b) and (c)”, read “It is therefore probable that this is the circumstance of origin of groups (b) and (c) as well”. Same par., end, for “auxiliary verbs” read “helping vowels”. In 1.4.9, end of p.72, for “other than the *maqfef*” read “and without the *maqfef*”. Same par., n.99, for “the construct pair” read “the noun in the construct state”. Same par., p.73, line 16, for “the nominal construct state is attracted to suffixed nouns” read “a pair of nouns, one being in the construct state, is to be regarded as equivalent to a noun with a possessive suffix”. For “a suffixed noun” read “a noun with a possessive suffix”. For “grasped as a single feature” read “felt to be the same phenomenon”. For “beset by analogies” read “obscured by analogies”. For “as befits languages” read “as is normal with languages”. For “without relating to the sequence” read “without considering the relationship to the flow of utterance”. At the end of this, two Hebrew grammatical terms are left untranslated. In 1.4.10, end, a Hebrew grammatical term is used without any explanation. For “may” read “might”, since the author wanted to emphasise doubt, not raise a possibility, and then put the word in italics corresponding to letter-spacing in the original. For “the Tiberian Hebrew parallel is evident from the gemination” read “the gemination is a clear parallel to Tiberian Hebrew”. In 1.5.1.3, for “we have encountered” read “we find”, and correct the vowels. In 1.5.2.0, start, for “an apparently abstract average” read “a sort of abstract average”. In line 11 from the end on p.78 insert “that although” before “the difference”, delete “nevertheless” at the start of the next sentence, and then join the sentences. In 1.5.3.2, for “without any real dissimilation” read “that is not actually dissimilation”. In 2.0.7, middle, for “root classes” read “morphological types”. In 2.0.9, the first lines on p.102 are unintelligible, partly, but only partly, due to a misprint in the original, this misprint being obvious and easily corrected anyway. In 2.14.12, end, for “on the day when they are anointed” read “on the day when he is anointed”. The editor has not understood that it is not the implications of the Masoretic pointing that are under discussion, but a different analysis assumed by some Samaritan grammarians. In 2.14.14, end, after “in place of the TH Nif’al form”, the translation leaves out the Hebrew word intended. In 2.14.17, middle, for “and indeed this entire series of developments is outside the Samaritan tradition” read “and indeed this entire series of developments does exist outside the Samaritan tradition”. The author means that the phenomena of Samaritan Hebrew under discussion are to be found in Masoretic Hebrew as well. In 2.15.0, end, for “the Aramaic way” read “Aramaisms”. In 8.3, n.1, for “even though they are short” read “when they are short”. The names assigned to the vowels here will make no sense to the reader, for the reasons explained earlier in this review. In 8.3, end, for “In fact it is surprising that...” read “Note the striking phenomenon that...”. In 8.9, end, for “Official Aramaic” read “Imperial Aramaic”.

There are several places where the translator and editor have both failed to understand a piece of Hebrew *in its context*. In 2.1.3.7, n.31, Ben-H.ayyim has done the reader the service of quoting, from a previous volume of this set, a sentence from a work by a Samaritan grammarian which the reader of the isolated English translation of this volume needs

to have on the page. (Would that the author or the editors had done this systematically throughout the book). Unfortunately, the translator and the editor have failed to understand either Ben-H.ayyim's Hebrew translation or the Arabic original. The context is the observation by this Samaritan grammarian that forms of what could be called "the second form of the heavy stem", i.e. forms like a pi^el but without doubling of the second root consonant and with a long vowel before the second root consonant (called by Ben-H.ayyim Pi^el B), are limited to certain types of root in the Pentateuch, namely verbs with no weak consonants, some Double ^eAyin roots, and some with *nun* or *pe* as the first root consonant. He then observes that the Hebrew language allows the use of this stem in all other roots — even though by chance the forms do not occur in the Pentateuch — except for roots with a guttural as the second or third consonant; and he adds that even with roots with *waw* or *yod* as the second root letter this can be done. Here is what is printed in the English translation. The words are taken from Ben-H.ayyim's translation of the Samaritan text, with Ben-H.ayyim's explanatory footnotes in the original inserted in the English translation printed here and marked by brackets: "It may be that in the language (i.e. outside the Pentateuch!) all those types (i.e. other than the strong verb, those similar, and those with a *nun* and a *pe*) serve in this part of the heavy stem except when its second or third radical is a guttural letter". The editors have failed to take in the Arabic original or the preceding text, and an ambiguity in Ben-H.ayyim's Hebrew has then been resolved the wrong way, so that "It is grammatically acceptable" has become "It may be". For "those similar" read "Double ^eAyin verbs". For "those with a *nun*" read "those with a *nun* as the first consonant". For "*pe*" read "*Pe Alef*", i.e. read the sequence of letters *pe* and *alef* as a grammatical symbol, not a letter-name. This last error is interesting. Ben-H.ayyim's original footnote in Hebrew did not give this last item, and he has added it for clarity this time, but the editors have missed the point of the addition. For "serve" read "can appear". For "except when its" read "excluding [only] those whose". The translator has had some difficulty with the content, but the editors ought to have understood the quotation *along with its context in the Samaritan grammatical treatise, and the implications of the Arabic original*. Other evidence of inability to handle Arabic in the editorial process is cited later in this review.

In the preface, the author says that he thought it necessary to add translations of the quotations from post-Biblical Hebrew, and to expand or abbreviate the quotations in certain cases (p.xiv top), to help readers unaccustomed to reading this kind of Hebrew. I have already expressed my opinion on the pointlessness of this kind of procedure. Actually, such quotations are not numerous. The examples that are purely linguistic are adequately handled. There are, however, two places where the quotation is exegetical, having the form of a halachic midrash, and in both these cases the editor has failed to understand the argument. In one case the result is obscurity, but in the other case the result is nonsense. In 2.4.5, p.140 top, there is a quotation from the Sifrei on Deuteronomy dealing with the phrase WYShBH BBYTK in XXI:13. The first word is misquoted. Then, the Sifrei is misquoted, with "in a house he uses" instead of "in a house they use". The reader has no way of working out the point of the argument. In 2.14.15, n.193, the error is both more serious and more prominent. The two Hebrew words YMWL WHMWL

should be HMWL YMWL, from Genesis XVII:13. The non-sensical Hebrew phrase YMWL HMWL GWY MLHWL' L' 'ShH should be W'ShH L' MLH WL' GWY HMWL YMWL, a tersely expressed halachic argument from a *piyut*. The translation "one who is circumcised may be circumcised" for HMWL YMWL is arrant nonsense. In both these cases the argument is set out in Hebrew that is easy to understand if the reader is at all acquainted with the style of Rabbinic texts.

There are numerous errors in the printing of Arabic words, and also in the romanised transcription of Arabic. We will take one example where the effect is to make the argument unintelligible. It is well known that one current within the Samaritan tradition of the pronunciation of Hebrew recognises fricative allophones of the stops, as does Masoretic Hebrew, and that there are grammatical treatises in Arabic in which the alternation of the allophones is shown by phonetic transcription in Arabic letters. One such Arabic treatise is quoted in 1.1.3, note 7. In the translation into English, the letter *dhâl* has become *dâl*, and *dâl* has become *dhal*, *thâ* has become *tâ*, and *tâ* has become *thâ*. This confusion, combined with unsatisfactory translation ("proposes" and "wrongly positioned"), has totally destroyed the argument. The confusion over the three vowels in the list of symbols at the start of the book and then frequently afterwards when the vowels are named would have been avoidable if the Arabic treatises had been consulted carefully.

Meanwhile, Macuch's grammar is still in print, and it always makes sense.

Balaclava (Melbourne), January 2003

I.R.M. BÓID

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TAL, A. — A Dictionary of Samaritan Aramaic. 2 vols. (Handbuch der Orientalistik, 1). E.J. Brill Publishers N.V., Leiden, 2000. (24 cm, XLIV, 967). ISBN 90-04-11645-1; ISSN 0169-9423. € 177,-.¹⁾

Das lang erwartete Wörterbuch zum samaritanischen Aramäisch liegt nun vor und füllt eine große Lücke innerhalb

¹⁾ Verwendete Abkürzungen:

AA = Ägyptisch-Aramäisch;
Akkad. = Akkadisch;
Arnold 1990 = W. Arnold, *Das Neuestaramäische. V. Grammatik*, Wiesbaden 1990;
Bergsträsser 1921 = G. Bergsträsser, *Glossar des nearamäischen Dialekts von Ma'lûla*, Leipzig 1921;
Brockelmann 1910 = C. Brockelmann, *Vergleichende Grammatik der semitischen Sprachen*, Berlin 1910;
Brockelmann 1928 = C. Brockelmann, *Lexicon Syriacum*, Halle 1928;
CAD = L. Oppenheim, *Chicago Assyrian Dictionary*, Chicago 1956-;
CPA = Christlich-Palästinisch-Aramäisch;
CCPA I = Ch. Müller-Kessler/M. Sokoloff, *The Christian Palestinian Aramaic Old Testament Version from the Early Period. A Corpus of Christian Palestinian Aramaic I*, Groningen 1997;
CCPA IIA = Ch. Müller-Kessler/M. Sokoloff, *The Christian Palestinian Aramaic New Testament Version from the Early Period. A Corpus of Christian Palestinian Aramaic IIA*, Groningen 1998;
CCPA IIB = Ch. Müller-Kessler/M. Sokoloff, *The Christian Palestinian Aramaic New Testament Version from the Early Period. Acts of Apostles and Epistles. A Corpus of Christian Palestinian Aramaic IIB*, Groningen 1998;
CCPA III = Ch. Müller-Kessler/M. Sokoloff, *The Forty Martyrs of the Sinai Desert, Eulogios, the Stone-Cutter, and Anastasia. A Corpus of Christian Palestinian Aramaic III*, Groningen 1996;

1990-1993); M.H. Goshen-Gottstein, *The Bible in the Syro-palestinian Version* (Jerusalem 1973); diverse Artikel von J. Margain zu kleineren SA Partikeln und die Texteditionen und Glossare bei Ch. Müller-Kessler und M. Sokoloff, *A Corpus of Christian Palestinian Aramaic* (Groningen 1996-1999). In anderen Fällen wurden trotz der Auflistung bestimmter Werke in der Bibliographie diese in der etymologischen Sektion nicht ausgewertet. Außerhalb der Schule von Ze'ev Ben-Hayyim und Abraham Tal erschienene Beiträge zum Samaritanischen werden auffallend selten zitiert oder herangezogen. Die Quellen vieler angeführter vergleichender Etymologien werden nicht genannt. Ganz besonders fallen extrem veraltete Zitate für das CPA auf, wo z.B. die Petersburger-Fragmente des Cyrill von Jerusalem, die H. Duensing in *Christlich-palästinisch-aramäische Texte und Fragmente*, Göttingen 1906, S. 41-50 identifiziert hatte, noch unter der Bezeichnung Hom. from J.P.N. Land, *Anecdota Syriaca* (Leiden 1875) firmieren.

Gewohnheitsbedürftig ist die Vorliebe des Autors, alle Worte nach Wurzeln, teilweise Schein-Wurzeln anzuordnen, wobei er das Lemma in der Übersetzung nicht in seiner semantisch verbalen Bedeutung, sondern zumeist in nominaler oder sogar abstrakter Bedeutung wiedergibt, nicht gerade die klassische Vorgehensweise in einem semitischen Wurzelwörterbuch. Vor allem bei ursprünglich zweiradikaligen Wurzeln führt dies zur Ansetzung hyperkorrekter Wurzeln, vgl. z.B. אהי 'brotherhood' S. 1. Absurd scheint eine hyperkorrekte Wurzelansetzung wie כמר 'priesthood' [S. 394], das der Autor vom Nomen כומר 'a non-Jewish priest' ableitet. כומר ist wahrscheinlich aus akkad. *kumāru* entlehnt, dort seit der altassyrischen Periode belegt, doch wahrscheinlich nicht-semitischen Ursprungs. Noch eigenartiger ist es, eine Wurzel דמס aus dem griechischen *δομός* S. 188 oder *δημοσία* S. 189 zu kreieren.

Sehr nützlich sind die systematischen Ausspracheangaben nach den Etymologien.

Zu den Eigenarten dieses Wörterbuches gehört auch die Aufspaltung eines identischen in zwei individuelle Lemmas, wenn die Wortbeispiele defektiv und plene geschriebene Varianten ausweisen, was zur Verwirrung des Benutzers und zur Aufblähung des Werkes führt.

Nachteilig wirkt sich ferner aus, daß bei den Targum-Manuskripten den Textbeispielen zumeist keine Belegstellen hinzugefügt wurden, abgesehen von den sehr späten, stark vom Hebräischen oder Arabischen beeinflussten Handschriften. Dies betrifft auch die Targum Onqelos beeinflussten späten Handschriften. Es kann eigentlich nicht vom Benutzer des Wörterbuchs erwartet werden, daß er gleichzeitig mit dem Wörterbuch die Targume des Samaritanisch-Aramäischen zur Hand hat. Angesichts großer Divergenzen in den Samaritanisch-Aramäischen Handschriften ist es doch entscheidend, ob etwa Variante A oder Variante J vorliegt.

Akkadische Etymologien werden oft ausgelassen, gelegentlich, nach ebenfalls unerfindlichen Prinzipien, doch auch angeführt. In solchen Fällen wäre gelegentlich statt des Hinweises auf die akkad. Wörterbücher der Hinweis auf die speziellere und kritischere Studie von S.A. Kaufman, *Akkadian Influences on Aramaic* (*Assyriological Studies* 19; Chicago 1974) hilfreich und ausreichend gewesen.

Sicherlich ist zu begrüßen, daß der Autor den SA-Dialekt zumeist nur mit den enger verwandten Nachbardialekten bzw., wenn relevant, mit dem Hebräischen und Arabischen vergleicht und auf zusätzliche etymologische Notierungen aus entfernteren semitischen Sprachen weitgehend verzichtet. Der

Rezensentin bleibt jedoch unklar, nach welchen Prinzipien das komparatistische Material aus dem Christlich-Palästinisch-Aramäischen (hier: סרא), dem Jüdisch-Palästinisch-Aramäischen (hier: א) und dem Qumran-Aramäischen (hier: מ"א, sowie aus Ma'lūla, Ḡubb 'Adīn and Baḥ'a, welches fast völlig ignoriert wurde (dazu nun W. Arnold, *Semitica Viva Series* 4/I-V, Wiesbaden 1990-1993) ausgewählt wurde, da in vielen der Fälle, bei denen der Aramaist und Semitist eine etymologische Erklärung erwarten würde, eine solche gänzlich fehlt. Während für das JPA noch zumeist Quellenbelege gegeben werden, ist der Benutzer beim CPA oft rettungslos verloren. Evangelienzitate scheinen dabei vorzugsweise aus dem späten, sehr korrupten Lektionar B ausgewählt worden zu sein, doch werden auch, ohne jeden Hinweis, Belege aus A oder C geben. Unter שבשב 'twig' [S. 869] findet sich einmal ein Hinweis auf Evangelium A, obgleich die Version B mit Johannes 12:13 *šwbsbyn ddqlyn* zitiert wird; die beste CPA-Handschrift MS T^a hat aber *šwbsbn ddqly[n]*. Für die Passagen des Alten Testaments scheint das aus dem späten 11. Jahrhundert stammende Lewis-Lektionar, publiziert als A.S. Lewis, *A Palestinian Syriac Lectionary* (London 1897), die Präferenz erhalten zu haben. Doch verschleiert das späte CPA-Material die tatsächliche lexikographische Situation in diesem Dialekt.

Die Rezensentin ist nicht der Ansicht, daß der SA Targum vom Targum Onqelos (אונקלוס = O) sehr beeinflusst ist, wie der Autor angibt, der häufig einzelne Lexeme mit dem Zusatz »aus TO« versieht. In vielen dieser Fälle (siehe dazu unten) kann dies gar nicht zutreffen, da das entsprechende Lemma auch im CPA vorhanden ist, und dieser Dialekt nun am allerwenigsten in den Verdacht geraten kann, irgendwie vom TO berührt worden zu sein. Die einfachste Interpretation scheint zu sein, daß das TO-Vokabular Teil des Standard-Literarisch-Aramäischen war, das ursprünglich in Palästina heimisch war, später aber von den Rabbinern nach Babylonien transportiert wurde, wo wenigstens nach Ansicht der Rezensentin Targum Onqelos und Jonathan verfaßt wurden; siehe dazu nun Ch. Müller-Kessler, 'The Earliest Evidence for Targum Onqelos from Babylonia and the Question of its Dialect and Origin', *Journal for the Aramaic Bible* 3 (2001) 181-198.

Einige der *nomina unitatis* (תמרה, חמרה, חמרה, דמעה, דמעה, דמעה, דמעה), deren Genus immer fem. ist, die Fem.-Endung aber nur im Sing. zeigen, dagegen eine mask. im Plur., werden unter inkorrekten Lemmata geführt (תמר, חמר, חמר, חמר, חמר, חמר). Sie bilden gemeinam. eine Gruppe, wenn sie auch nicht alle für jeden Dialekt belegt sind; vgl. die Listen in Nöldeke 1898, 53; Dalman 1905, 197; Arnold 1990, 290, 294 ff., 321, teilweise 339; Müller-Kessler 1991, 109/110. Unsicherheiten sind auch bei der Verwendung des grammatikalischen Terminus *pluralia tantum* festzustellen und bei der korrekten Angabe des Genus bei Nomina.

Leider ist auch zu konstatieren, daß das vorliegende Wörterbuch zahlreiche störende typographische Irrtümer enthält und den Eindruck hastiger Fertigstellung vermittelt. Der Verlag scheint wieder einmal keine Hilfestellung geleistet zu haben. Das gilt auch für das sehr schlecht lesbare Druckbild, besonders bei einigen der Schrifttypen, die für den normalen Leser viel zu klein sind. Abkürzungsverzeichnis und Bibliographie bilden eine Einheit, enthalten aber zuviele ärgerliche Versehen und Fehler, gravierende Unterschiede zwischen den hebräischen und englischen Sektionen, Unsicherheiten in der Schreibweise fremdsprachlicher Literatur, insbesondere bei französischen und deutschen Titeln und auch Eigennamen.

Einmal zitierte Werke wie R. Macuch, *Grammatik des Samaritanisch-Aramäischen*, Berlin 1982; Margain, Sefarad??? oder M.H. Segal, *A Grammar Mishnaic Hebrew*, Oxford 1980 fehlen dort. Sprachliche Untersuchungen von Z. Ben-Hayyim, A. Tal und anderen Autoren werden in der hebräischen Abkürzungsliste nur nach dem Titel der Sammelschrift gelistet, ohne Nennung des Aufsatztitels und der Seitenzahlen. Es macht schon einige Mühe, solchen Abkürzungen nachzugehen wie z.B. זב"ח oder ת"מ. Auf die mannigfachen Ungereimtheiten in diesen Abschnitten kann im Folgenden aus Platzgründen nicht weiter eingegangen werden.

Es ist schade, daß diese aufgeführten Defizite und Versehen die Ergebnisse der langjährigen Anstrengungen des Autors in der Sammlung und Ordnung eines schwierig zugänglichen Materials etwas verdunkeln. Nur ein mit den westaram. Dialekten und der aktuellen wissenschaftlichen Literatur sehr gut vertrauter Aramaist dürfte sich in diesem Wörterbuch ohne längere Einarbeitung zurecht finden. Die Rezensentin fürchtet, daß dieser Kreis sehr klein sein wird. Keinesfalls ist jedoch das aus den benachbarten Dialekten beigesteuerte Parallelmaterial ungeprüft zu übernehmen, da in fast jedem zweiten bis dritten Zitat, Fehlzitate und Verschreibungen zu notieren sind.

Bemerkungen zu einzelnen Lexemen:

Die folgenden Bemerkungen basieren zum Teil auf Stichproben, welche die Rezensentin für jeden zweiten Buchstaben durchführte, teilweise mit einem Schwergewicht auf dem CPA als chronologisch, morphologisch und lexikalisch nahestehendem Dialekt.

ארע 'arm' [S. 10] ist fem., nicht mask., da es paarweise begegnet. Weshalb ist es entsprechend seiner Wurzel dann nicht unter דרע aufgelistet?

אחי 'brotherhood' [S. 18]: Sollte unter dem Lemma אח gelistet werden. Eine Wurzel אחי existiert nicht.

אחר 'delay, end' [S. 19]: תאחרון kann kaum auf Targum Onqelos basieren, da die Verbalwurzel im Westaram. gut belegt ist; siehe CPA Af. *whr* 'to delay' Mt 25:5C¹P^dP^e, Lk 1:21P^e CCPA IIA.

ארומן 'craftsman' [S. 42] und seine Ableitungen basieren auf Akkad. *ummānu*, Kaufman 1974, 109 (SA dort nicht erwähnt); erst in einem zweiten Schritt wurde es im SA zu /qattāl/, da das SA besonders dazu tendiert, vorderes /u/ zu /a/ werden, zu lassen.

ארגון 'purple' [S. 59]: Weshalb finden sich mit ארגון und ארגמן zwei Eintragungen für ein- und dasselbe Lemma, nur weil die Orthographie des SA hier schwankt?

ארן 'chest' [S. 64]: Frühere und spätere CPA-Versionen zeigen hier auch den totalen Verlust des Gutturals in *m š lrn* Lk 7:14P^e CCPA IIA, *ḫ lrn* A.

ארנבה 'hare' [S. 64]: Korrigiere zu n. f.

ארוסה 'betrothed' [S. 65]: *rys*, nicht *rysh* begegnet seltener im CPA. Die bessere CPA-Variante ist das pass. Part. *rys* Lk 1:27C³ CCPA IIA wie im SA als Verbaladjektiv gebraucht, aber nicht als Nomen.

אשה 'fire' [S. 67]: Das zutreffende Lemma für 'Feuer' ist im Westaram. wie im SA אשה, jedoch nicht אש, da אשה im Aram. nur mit der Fem.-Endung erscheint, auch in der Uruk-Beschwörung im Status absolutus als *iš-šá-*. Der etymologische Abschnitt sollte daher besser unter אשה und nicht unter dem hebr. Lemma אש stehen.

¹את 'sign' [S. 70]: Das Wort ist fem., nicht mask.; es fehlt ein englisches Äquivalent.

²אתה 'you' [S. 70]: Dieses Stichwort sollte an zweiter Stelle unter der korrekten westaram. Form את stehen, und nicht unter hebr. אתה notiert sein, da eine offensichtliche Konfusion mit dem aram. Pronomen vorliegt. Daß die älteren aram. Dialekte את(ה) gebrauchen, ist für diese Periode nur von sekundärer Bedeutung.

באש 'badness, evil' [S. 78-79]: Weshalb wird nur bei den JPA-Etymologien zwischen 'evil' und 'ill' differenziert, aber nicht ebenso beim CPA? Daß die Orthographie des SA weit besser als allgemein angenommen ist, demonstriert der Gebrauch der Wurzel באש in dem semantischen Bereich 'to be ill, weak' und 'to be evil'. Wie im CPA schreibt das SA konsequent באש mit Aleph, wenn die Bedeutung 'to be ill', 'illness' vorliegt, jedoch mit Yod, wenn 'to be evil' gemeint ist; vgl. die Glossare of CCPA I-III, V.

בגלל 'because' [S. 79]: בגלל Konj.; die englische Wiedergabe muß 'because' sein, da 'because of' die Präposition wäre. Die Übersetzung des ersten SA-Beispiels sollte 'close the mouth of the snake, because it destroyed life' lauten. Tiere ohne Eigennamen werden im Englischen als Neutrum aufgefaßt.

בד 'oil' [S. 80]: CPA and SA basieren nicht auf Hebr. בית הבד. Es erscheint öfter in Kompositausdrücken, u.a. in CPA *byt bd* 'oil-mill' CSR^P = Syr. no. 16, fol. 45 ra, ll. 14/5 = Land 1875, 181, zutreffend emendiert von Duensing 1906, 72, Müller-Kessler [in Vorbereitung]. In dem CPA-Text wird *byt bd* deutlich von *m'sr* 'oil-press' r b Z. 1 geschieden, doch wird an der SA-Stelle בדך auch als 'your oil-press' gebraucht, nicht 'your oil offering'. בד 'a press beam, tank' ist ebenso ein *terminus technicus* für die Weinpresse. ¹בד and ²בד sollten beide unter demselben Lemma als '(oil)beam, branch' aufgeführt sein. Weshalb wird Hebr. und Engl. die Bedeutung. תרומה מן השמן 'oil offering' angesetzt, wenn die hebr. Übersetzung der SA-Passage בדך בית הבד lautet?

בדיל part, of cause [S. 81]: Eine Partikel *bdyl* ist so nie im CPA bezeugt. Die zitierte Passage lautet *lbdyl my' dṭwṗn'* Lewis 1897, 89.

בדק 'breach, spoiling' [S. 82]: Die SA-Stelle hängt in seiner Bedeutung kaum von der Targum Onqelos-Version ab. Eine CPA-Parallele fehlt in der etymologischen Sektion.

בהל 'haste' [S. 83]: Die Wurzel muß hier 'to be movable, be loosened' bedeuten, parallel zu ופזין V, vgl. Syr. *pzyz* 'easily movable' Brockelmann 1928, 561; auch das CPA kennt dies als *w'str: w g: ydy' d'dr: 'y' b'ydh* »and the sinews of the arms slackened in his hand« Gn 49:24T CCPA I.

²בוז 'spoiling, robbery' [S. 85]: Warum werden für *bzz* 'to plunder' mit *bzw* and *bzz* zwei Wurzeln angesetzt? Das Verbum בוז [S. 89] 'to plunder' gehört zu den Verba mediae geminatae, die wie die Verba mediae infirmae behandelt werden, und der Infinitiv constructus לבוז ist die erwartete westaram. Form für die Verba II=III oder Verba IIw/y, die aus dem Hebr. resultiert; vgl. im CPA die *figura etymologica* des Verbums *mwt*, *mwt ymwt* »he should die« LESC 84a:2 CCPA III. Ein umgekehrter Fall ist die Wurzel בוה 'despise', bei der *bzy* zu *bzw* oder *bzz* wurde.

בוץ 'linen' [S. 86]: Hinzuzufügen ist CPA *bws* Ex 26:31V CCPA I. Die SA-Varianten können kaum von Targum Onqelos beeinflusst sein, da בוץ gutes Westaram. ist.

בי 'house' [S. 87]: Warum sollte das Lexem in בית und aufgespalten werden?

בין 'between' [S. 94]: Die Präposition ist gemeinaram.

בעט 'kicking' [S. 107]: Vgl. CPA *dq[š]y ly dyb'wt lmqwt'* »it is difficult for me to kick against goads« Cyr 10:18Pⁱ CCPA V (= Duensing 1906, 57).

בער 'burning' [S. 109]: Vgl. CPA *bnwr' db'r'* »with fire that burns« 2Thess 1:8C² CCPA IIB; *hy b'r'* 'it (the fire) burns' Cyr 17:8Pⁱ CCPA V (= Land 1875, 191).

גבול 'eye-brow' [S. 126]: Das Nomen ist gemeinarm. Die SA-Formen sind teilweise nur im Plur. belegt, doch handelt es sich nicht um ein Plur. tant. (siehe oben).

גבול 'hunchback' [S. 126]: Besser 'hunchbacked'. Es liegt kaum ein Targum Onqelos-Einfluß vor. Auch das CPA verwendet es gelegentlich in der späten Periode; vgl. *gbyn* Schultheß 1903, 33.

גול 'fledgling' [S. 135]: Vgl. CPA *wgwzl dywn* Lv 12:6C⁷ CCPA I; korrigiere im Glossar CCPA I *wgwzl dywn* "... *lwt khn'* Lv 12:7 zu Lv 12:6.

גוז 'shearer' [S. 140]: *גוזי עאנה* sollte übersetzt werden als »he went up with his sheepshearers«, nicht »to his sheepshearers«. SA versteht die Stelle dagegen anders als die hebr. Vorlage. Ein solch speziellerer Gebrauch von *עם* sollte unter *עם* erscheinen.

גוי 'recompense' [S. 140]: Korrigiere für das CPA *ṭ'by* zu *ṭ'bn*. Der Autor läßt den Benutzer völlig darüber im unklaren, woher er das CPA-Zitat Ps 38:20 nimmt. Eine vollständige Edition aller biblischen Passagen existiert bisher nicht, und es kann kaum vom Leser erwartet werden, selbst die vorhandenen Handschriften durchzusuchen.

גמר 'coal' [S. 151]: Das Lemma sollte als *גמרה* gelistet werden wie *תאנה* 'fig' [S. 939], da es eine Fem.-Endung im Sing. aufweist, im Plur. aber eine mask. (siehe oben).

גרי 'provocation' [S. 158]: Hinzuzufügen ist CPA Pa. *mgr:yn pl:gn lplg* »we compete against one another« Gal 5:26C² CCPA IIB; *גרי* ist aram. und nur verwandt mit akkad. *gerû*.

גרע 'reduction' [S. 159]: Hinzuzufügen ist CPA Pa. *w'pq ṭyhwn dygr: ṭwn r:šyhwn* »and pay for shaving their heads« Acts 21:24C² CCPA IIB.

דמס 'building' [S. 188]: Die bessere CPA-Variante ist *nqtwr: lhwm bnyh ddwms'* »we will bind the connecting joint of the building of house« Cyr 11Pⁱ CCPA V.

דמע 'tear' [S. 189]: Die Eintragung sollte *דמעה* lauten wie bei *תאנה* 'fig', da es sich um ein fem. Normen handelt, das im Plur. eine Mask.-Endung aufweist. Es fehlt offensichtlich ein י nach *דמע* im Text of Tibat Marqe, und es hätte schon eines Kommentars bedurft, um mit dem Autor zu übersetzen »tears (<דמע>) dropped from his eyes like rain«; auf S. 464 und 666 findet man für dieselbe Passge »the tear (<דמע>) of his eye drops like rain«, S. 464 hätte als »his eyes« wie in der Hebr.-Übersetzung *עיניו* wiedergegeben werden müssen.

דקיקה 'illness' [S. 193]: Dieser Krankheitsname ist unter einer Reihe von Krankheiten *אשתה וערייתה* auf einem JPA Amulett aus Ḥorvat Kanaf belegt. Eine vergleichende Etymologie wäre hier wünschenswert gewesen.

די 'confession' [S. 215]: Die Eintragung sollte unter *די* erfolgen, da die hier angesetzten Pa.-Formen reguläre Af.-Formen eines ursemitischen *Iw*-Verbums sind, die zu *Iy*-Verben im Kanaanäischen, Ugaritischen und Aramäischen wurden, und deshalb dieses ursprüngliche *w* teilweise dann noch in den Af.-Formen zeigen. Das CPA verwendet *ydy* in derselben Bedeutung und im Af., kennt im Gegensatz zum SA dazu aber auch ein *Ištaf*.

זהר 'scarlet' [S. 223]: *זהורי* ist nach den Belegen im Wörterbuch nur als *זעורי* in SA belegt. Es ist auf keinen Fall mit der

Wurzel *zhr* 'to shine' zu verbinden, da historisch schreibende Dialekte wie das CPA, vgl. *zhwry* Mk 15:17P^e CCPA IIA, *zyhwryt'* Ex 28:50 CCPA I, sowie das Syr. *zhwry* ein *h* zeigen; dies auch im QA. Es handelt sich um ein altes Kulturwort mit unbekannter Etymologie.

זוגי 'pair' [S. 223]: Die angeführte Passage Lk 2:24 mit dem Zitat Lv 15:14 sollte im älteren CPA *tr:yn šw:pnyyn* lauten und nicht *zwg dšwpnyyn*, vgl. *tr:yn šwpnyyn* Lv 12:8C⁷ CCPA I. *zwg* wird im Westaram. als Fem. behandelt, da ein griech. Neutrum vorliegt, vgl. *w'zl' zwg' ṭb'* (MS sic) 'and the worthy pair came' Cyr 6:15Pⁱ CCPA V.

זור 'turning aside' [S. 228]: Eine Beeinflussung aus Targum Onqelos ist unwahrscheinlich, da das Verbum bereits in frühen CPA-Handschriften begegnet, vgl. *z'r:w bny:nš' mn qwšt'* »the human beings turned aside from truth« Cyr 15:9Pⁱ CCPA V (= Land 1875, 195).

זחך 'crawling, creeping' [S. 229]: Die CPA-Wurzel *zhp*, gelegentlich *z'p* geschrieben, scheint eher mit Akkad. *saḥāpu* 'to drive out' zu verbinden zu sein, und nicht mit Arab. *zhp* 'to creep'. Alternative Schreibungen *s* anstelle von *z* erscheinen im SA und CPA auch bei *shr* und *zhr* 'moon'.

זחמה 'sourness' [S. 280]: *זחמה* 'leavened' ist ein pass. Part. Af.; vgl. auch CPA *sybhd' myr kwlh. gblth mhm'* »a little sour dough leavens the whole dough« Gal 5:9C² CCPA IIB.

זמר 'wine, vinegar; yeast' [S. 280]: Eine frühe CPA-Variante hat die Schreibung *'myr* 'leaven' Gal 5:9C² CCPA IIB wie im SA, dem späteren *hmyr* Lk 13:21A nahekommend. Es wäre darüber zu diskutieren, inwiefern die Bedeutung 'kindsman' als Bedeutung 4 unter diesem Lemma erscheinen sollte.

זנוך Henoch [S. 282]: Weshalb werden drei Lemmata für ein- und denselben Eigennamen angesetzt?

זסך 'earthenware' [S. 287]: Vgl. CPA *hsp* 'earthenware sherd' FMSD 90a:9 CCPA III (= Lewis 1912, 83, a9).

זפי 'covering' [S. 288]: Vgl. CPA *hpyt'* 'veil' 2Kor 3:13T^b CCPA IIB (= Schultheß 1903, 68).

זצר 'the protuberance of the liver' [S. 291]: Korrigiere CPA-Etymologie *whšr kbdh* zu *whšr kbd'* Lv 8:25C⁷ CCPA I (= Lewis 1909, 4).

זקל 'field' [S. 292]: *זקל* wird immer als Fem. behandelt, doch tritt nur im Plur. die Fem.-Endung wie bei *אורה* 'way, road' an; das SA scheint eine fem. Nebenform *זקלה* zu kennen.

זקק 'law, legislation' [S. 292]: Es liegt wiederum ein älteres hebr. Lehnwort vor, das fest im Westaram. verankert ist, so auch im CPA *hḡhḡq* 'edict, order' Lk 1:3P^c CCPA IIA; späte Testimonia haben *hḡwq* ABC.

זרי 'cake' [S. 294]: Hinzuzufügen ist CPA *hw:yn* 'cakes' Ex 12:39V CCPA I.

זרק' 'loins' [S. 296]: Es liegt Plur. oder ein fixierter Dual vor, jedenfalls kein Plur. tant.

זרשה 'forest' [S. 298]: Das Wort hat im SA eine Mask.-Form, nicht Fem., deshalb sollte das Lemma *זרש* lauten.

זבי 'deer' [S. 302]: Hinzuzufügen ist CPA *ṭby'* Dt 12:22V CCPA I (= Duensing 1906, 123).

זבע 'minting' [S. 302]: Vgl. CPA *Peal ṭby'* 'hewn' 2Kor 3:7T^b CCPA IIB; vgl. auch Ch. Müller-Kessler, 'Neue Materialien zum Christlich-Palästinisch-Aramäischen Lexikon I', in: M.J. Geller, J.C. Greenfield, M. Weitzman (Hrsg.), *Studia Aramaica* (Journal of Semitic Studies Monograph 4; Oxford 1995) 154.

זיר 'augur' [S. 310]: Lies 'augury', not 'augur'. Das Augurium ist eine spezielle Art der Weissagung mittels Vogelbe-

obachtung. Ist diese Bedeutung vom Autor gemeint, oder doch nur allgemein Divination, wobei im Aram. zwischen טיר 'augury' und einer anderen Wurzel קסם 'devination' unterschieden wird? Das Stichwort bzw. die einzige vorhandene Textstelle sollten dann aber auch als 'do not augur' wiedergegeben werden.

טוב 'goodness, kindness' [S. 303]: Ein Abstraktnomen dieser Form existiert nicht.

מיטב 'improvement' [S. 305]: Die Eintragung sollte unter טוב gebucht sein.

טחן 'grinding' [S. 309]: Die zitierte CPA-Passage entstammt der späten und korrupten Handschrift B; eine bessere CPA-Variante ist *tr:tyn yh:n ṭh:nn bḥd' rhy* Mt 24:41P^d CCPA IIA.

טלפח 'lentil' [S. 314]: Das korrekte Lemma ist טלפחה, da es im Sing. fem. טלפחתי ist, aber die mask. Pluralendung טלפחי aufweist. טלפחין ist auch kein Plur. tant. (siehe oben). טלפחתי ist gemeinaram., vgl. CPA *ṭwlwphṭ* 'a part under the mill-stone of an oilpress (= Kelterbesen)' unidentifizierte Homilie Land 1875, 181, 12; im Neuwestaram. ist häufig der Sing. mit Fem.-Endung belegt, siehe *ṭlub^ehta* Arnold 1990, 339; die Stelle kann nicht von Targum Onqelos beeinflusst sein.

יבוסאי 'Jebusite' [S. 328]: Es liegt ein Adjektiv vor wie ארמאי 'pagan' [S. 63], zumal alle Gentilizia als Adjektive zu betrachten sind.

יברוה 'mandrake' [S. 329]: Es handelt sich um kein Plur. tant., sondern um ein Nomen, das im SA nur im Plur. belegt ist.

יום 'day' [S. 338]: Weder der Eintrag איממה noch יום sind fem. im SA oder im Gemeinaram., noch sind die Beispiele unter יום Plur. tant. im abstrakten Sinne, sondern nur regelmäßige mask. Pluralformen. יום hätte als erstes Lemma vor אימם angeführt gehört, da אימם eine sekundäre erweiterte Form mit lokativ-adverbial Endung -m ist, siehe Brockelmann 1910, 474.

יריעה 'a sheet of linen' [S. 361]: Es handelt sich wohl um einen Zeltvorhang, der jedoch nicht aus Leinen besteht, sondern wohl eher aus Leder. Hinzuzufügen ist CPA *ryr* Ex 26:5V CCPA I; das Wort ist wahrscheinlich nicht hebr. Herkunft, da es im Aram. weiter verbreitet ist und bereits in neuassyrischen Verwaltungstexten begegnet; siehe dazu den Vorschlag von Th. Kwasman in S. Dalley, *The Tablets from Fort Shalmaneser*, Oxford, 1984, 53, sowie Archiv für Orientforschung 36, 1986, 359.

כיוב 'pain' [S. 373]: Vgl. CPA *kywb* 'ill repute' 2Kor 6:8C² CCPA IIB, das eine identische Nominalform zeigt.

כבד 'liver' [S. 374]: Hinzuzufügen ist CPA *kbd* Lv 8:25C⁷ CCPA I.

כמן 'liying in wait, ambush' [S. 392]: Vgl. CPA *'b:dyn lh kymn* »they prepared for him an ambush« Acts 25:3C² CCPA IIB (= Lewis 1909, 90); siehe bereits Lewis 1912, 36; *whw mkmn 'lyh. dyšr' yth*. 'he lay in wait for her to let her stumble' VAQ Duensing 1906, 11, 19-21, 157.

כמר 'priesthood' [S. 394]: Es handelt sich um 'a non-Jewish priest' in Gegensatz zu כהן. Die CPA-Stelle lautet korrekt *kwmr' dy dhw' dzyws m' dhw' qwdm mdynt* Acts 14:13P^h CCPA IIB.

כרי 'heap' [S. 410]: Anstelle von *'myr* Hom. ist die CPA-Stelle nun *'byd* zu lesen.

כתן 'cotton' [S. 416]: Eine bessere CPA-Variante ist *ḥmš'* *kytn* 'linen' Ex 9:31 Lewis 1897, 63.

כתר 'crown' [S. 417]: Das Wort wurde wahrscheinlich über

das Hebr. in das Westaram. entlehnt, ist aber nicht hebr. Ursprungs; siehe dazu A. Salvesen, »*כתר*« (Esther 1:11; 2:17; 6:8) 'Something to do with a Camel'?« *Journal of Semitic Studies* 44, 1999, 35-45; es ist belegt im CPA als *kt'r* Ex 28:40 CCPA I.

לאי [S. 422] und לעי 'toil' [S. 441] sind identische Verbalwurzeln, basierend auf לאא. Sie sollten eher unter einem einzigen Eintrag erscheinen, da die verschiedenen Schreibungen nur auf der Verwechslung der Gutturale basieren. Dasselbe gilt für die Eintragungen bei Sokoloff 1990, 284. Im QA and CPA erscheinen ebenfalls Schreibweisen mit *h* und *'*, so ילה [א] Iob 39:10 10QtgJob und *lhy* Schultheß 1903, 101, aber *l'*: *'yn* Cyr 13:19Pⁱ CCPA V. לאי ist kein hebr. Lehnwort, da die Wurzel in einigen semit. Sprachen belegt ist.

לבך 'seizing' [S. 424]: Korrigiere CPA *lbk 'ly* Ps 17:9 Horol 30 zu *lbkw yty* Ps 16:9 Horol 30a, da die CPA-Tradition der LXX-Einteilung folgt.

לו 'almond' [S. 428]: Es ist bemerkenswert, daß JPA and CPA ein anderes Wort für 'almond' gebrauchen, JPA לו Sokoloff 1990, 122 und CPA *gw[z]* Jer 1:11P^a CCPA I.

לוט 'curse' [S. 428]: Korrigiere CPA *kl* zu *kwl*.

לוי 'joining' [S. 429]: Korrigiere CPA *bny lwy* Lk 2:44B zu *bny lwythwn*.

לוי *optative participle* [S. 429]: CPA Ps 118:5, nicht 119, da das Alte Testament im CPA der LXX-Einteilung folgt.

לוש 'kneading' [S. 430]: Das CPA-Beispiel Joel 4:10 hätte *lwšw* 'forge!' übersetzt werden sollen, da gegenüber der üblichen westaram. mit 'to knead' eine leicht abweichende Bedeutung vorliegt.

לעלע 'worm' [S. 432]: Das Lemma steht zwischen להח and להי an der falschen Stelle.

להם 'food' [S. 433]: Eine Passage *wnsb lḥm wzyq dmyyn* Gn 21:14 ist mir nicht für das CPA bekannt; es handelt sich um ein Zitat aus Targum Neofiti.

להש 'whispering' [S. 434]: Die CPA-Stelle bei Land 1875 ist zu lesen *lhr:šy'gr wllhw:šy'* »but for the sorcerers and diviners (beide Nomina sind *nomina agentis* /qattāl/, /qātōl/)« Cyr 4:37Pⁱ CCPA V (= Duensing 1906, 50).

לילי 'night' [S. 435]: Korrigiere CPA *dbw'* zu *dbwr* Mt 2:14B.

תלמיד 'pupil' [S. 439]: Das Wort ist aus dem Akkad. in das Aram. entlehnt, da eine Nominalform /taprīs/ für *nomina agentis* auf das Akkad. beschränkt ist; siehe Kaufman 1974, 107.

לעורב 'jester' [S. 440]: Es muß *qātōl* statt *qāṭol* sein.

לפיד 'torch' [S. 442]: Die Eintragung basiert auf dem griech. Plur. von *λαμπάς, λαμπάδος*, wie insbesondere frühe Varianten im CPA bezeugen, *lm:Pdyhwn* 'their (f.) lamps« Mt 25:3C¹P CCPA IIA, aber *lPydyhyn* Mt 25:7P^c CCPA IIA. Das letztere korreliert mit SA לפיד und teilweise mit JPA לפד.

לקי 'blow, strike' [S. 443]: Korrigiere CPA Ex 9:32 zu 9:31.

מן 'since, during' [S. 475]: Es handelt sich um eine Konjunktion, nicht um einen »marker of a simultaneous action«, vergleichbar dem CPA, *mkr:yn 'wn dḥlth dmr': lbny:nš' mn 'nn mPy:syn* »Therefore we know the fear of the Lord, while we persuade people.« 2Cor 5:11C² CCPA IIB; *mn 'b:dyn dy ṭb:t' l' nh'. mt'y:qyn* »While doing good deeds, we are not growing weary.« Gal 6:9C² CCPA IIB.

מן ד 'since' [S. 475]: Das CPA teilt den Gebrauch dieser spezifischen Konjunktion im Westaram. mit SA and JPA, vgl. *wmn dl' y':klwn dy'qrbwn yth lh* »and when they could not bring him nearer« Mk 2:4C¹ CCPA IIA (= Lewis 1909, 72);

siehe schon E.Y. Kutscher, *Studies in Galilean Aramaic*, Bar-Ilan 1976, 51-58.

ש 'which' [S. 476]: Das Korrelativ sollte als 'who' übersetzt werden.

מן 'what?' [S. 476]: Die Interrogativpartikel ist ebenfalls im CPA belegt, *mn hw gr dn drb* »what is greater?« Mt 23:19C¹ CCPA II A (= Lewis 1909, 50); für JPA siehe Sokoloff 1990, 317a.

מסכן 'poverty' [S. 479]: Hinzuzufügen ist < Akkad. *muškē-num*.

משש 'grope' [S. 491]: Hinzuzufügen ist CPA *m's lrn* Lk 7:14P⁸ CCPA IIA (= Land 1875, 152).

מתן 'waiting' [S. 492]: Hinzufügen ist CPA *hwy:nn mmt:nyn* Af. 'to delay' Acts 27:7C² CCPA IIB (= Lewis 1909, 98).

גוד 'dragging, pulling' [S. 497]: Lies CPA *kwl* anstelle von *kl* Jo 4:18 Lewis 1902.

גוד 'beating' [S. 499]: Lies CPA *ngwdyn* anstelle von *ngwdym* Is 50:6 Lewis 1897.

גוד 'workmanship' [S. 502]: Korrigiere CPA *hmš'* zu *hm:yš'* Ex 26:27V CCPA I.

גוד 'light' [S. 505]: Lies CPA *yrwšlym* anstelle von *yrwšlm* Is 60:1 Lewis 1897.

גוד 'sleep' [S. 509]: Das CPA hat bessere und ältere Textvarianten, *n'm:w [kwl]hwn whww [dm]ykn* Mt 25:5P^d, *n'm:y kwllhyn whwy dm'ykn* P^c CCPA IIA.

גוד 'fire' [S. 512]: Das Nomen ist im SA (נורה תיכלנה) »the fire will devour us« und meistens auch Gemeinaram. fem., in der älteren CPA-Periode immer. Die Angaben in Spitalers Ma'lūla-Grammatik betreffend des JPA und CPA sind nicht ganz korrekt.

גוד 'to practice magic' [S. 516]: Die Wurzel bedeutet gemeinaram. immer 'sorcery', nicht 'divination'; siehe קסם; der Gebrauch differiert vom Hebr. Das CPA-Zitat *l' lhlyn dmnh:šyn* »not to these who practice magic« entstammt der Passage Cyr 4:37Pⁱ CCPA V (= Duensing 1906, 50-51).

גוד 'baker' [S. 518]: Entlehnt aus Akkad. *nuḫatimmu*.

גוד 'women' [S. 550]: Die Wurzel von נשין ist *nš* und nicht נשי.

נתן 'giving' [S. 554]: Obwohl im CPA das Ersatzverb für *yhb* 'geben' im Imperfekt und Infinitiv *yt* ist, übernommen wohl aus dem Syr., *ntl*, ist bemerkenswert, daß einige der älteren CPA-Handschriften hier noch das Imperfekt von *ntn* verwenden, *ytn (lh) mr'* 2Tim 1:16, 180 CCPA IIB, *y'r'n lkwn* Joel 2:19T CCPA I, beides Fragmente aus der Kairoer Geniza; *'tn lhwn* Mt 24:45C¹ CCPA IIA, stammt aus einer Hs., die stark vom Ostaram. beeinflusst ist; siehe Ch. Müller-Kessler, 'Die frühe christlich-palästinisch-aramäische Evangelienhandschrift CCR1 übersetzt durch einen ostaramäischen (syrischen) Schreiber?' *Journal for the Aramaic Bible* 1, 1999, 79-86. *ntn* erscheint ebenfalls im Infinitiv in dem idiomatischen Ausdruck *msb wmtn* 'Nehmen und Geben = Geschäfte machen' Phil 4:15D¹ CCPA IIB.

סבט 'tongs' [S. 559]: Die akkad. Etymologie *šabātu* hat keine Relevanz für die Bedeutung des Wortes im SA, da dies hier dem Hebr. entlehnt ist.

מסגין 'jointed legs' [S. 566]: Es liegt entweder ein fixierter Dual oder ein Plur. vor, jedoch kein Plur. tant.

סדר 'order' [S. 568]: CPA hat *wyh:n sdr:n bbyth:wn ṭb:n* Ti 2:5 CCPA IIB.

סדר 'blemish' [S. 570]: Bedeutung 2 ist adjektivisch in der Bedeutung 'ill', nicht 'blemish'.

סוב 'old age' [S. 572]: weder das SA, noch das JPA und CPA zeigen den Wandel der Verba II' zu einer Wurzel IIw.

Lediglich wegen des Gutturalschwunds erscheint 'gelegentlich nicht mehr. Vgl. CPA *whw' kd s'b smw'yl* 1Sam 8:1 CCPA I.

סוס 'horse' [S. 574]: Das CPA gebracht nur die aram. Form *swsy'*, jedoch nicht die kurze hebr. *sws*.

סחף 'scattering' [S. 578]: Vgl. zu dieser Schreibweise für das CPA den Kommentar in CCPA I, 216-217.

סימן 'sign' [S. 584]: Hinzuzufügen wäre auch das CPA, das hier näher zum Griech. steht, *hyk mnhwn symyw:nyn lqyt'* 'like signs of them for the summer' Cyr 9:8Pⁱ CCPA V (= Land 1875, 199).

סיעה 'group' [S. 584]: Hinzuzufügen ist CPA *sy':yhwn dkwkb:y'* 'group of stars' Cyr 9:8Pⁱ CCPA V (= Land 1875, 199).

סכה 'thorn, peg' [S. 600]: *swky pdnykwn* im CPA ist ein *terminis technicus* 'coulters of your ploughs', hier nicht in das Hebr. übersetzt.

סטון 'a color' [S. 600]: Das Wort stammt kaum aus Targum Onqelos, sondern ist iran. Herkunft, mit der Bedeutung 'sixty colours, multicoloured', siehe Sh. Shaked, 'Items of Dress and Other Objects in Common Use: Iranian Loanwords in Jewish Babylonian Aramaic', *Irano-Judaica* 3, 1994, 112-114.

ספי 'consumption, death' [S. 603]: Die zitierte CPA-Stelle gehört zu ספי 'lip' S. 604, vgl. dafür *mspy ly* Phil 2:26P^a CCPA IIB.

עאן 'small cattle' [S. 615]: Hinzuzufügen ist CPA *'td ythwn hyk 'n' lnykyst'* »prepare them like small cattle for slaughter« Jer 12:3C⁸ CCPA I (= Goshen-Gottstein 1973, 85).

עז 'female goat' [S. 630]: goat meint im Englischen bereits das weibliche Tier; עז geht im Aram. bzw. im Semit. generell auf eine Wurzel *עזו zurück, nicht auf *עזו, vgl. den Status constructus Sing. *'nz* im Syr. Brockelmann 1928, 535 und den Sing. emph. im Reichsaram. *'עזו* Aḥiqar TAD 1.1.167. עז impliziert nicht 'small cattle', sondern ist Teil des Kleinviehs neben 'Schafen'.

עזי 'reckless' [S. 630]: Es handelt sich um keine Denominierung von עז 'goat', sondern um eine sekundäre Wurzel von עזי 'to be strong', die Aram. auch aufgefaßt werden kann als 'awe-inspiring', vgl. KBA *dlybt 'zyzt'* 'the awe-inspiring Dilbat' Montgomery 1913, 213, 28:5 < Akkad. *ezzu* CAD E; schwache Verbalwurzeln tendieren von einer Gruppe zur anderen zu wechseln.

עויב 'blemish' [S. 632]: Es handelt sich um die SA-Schreibweise von עויב; sie muß nicht von arab. *'yb* abgeleitet werden, da die Nominalform auch im CPA nachzuweisen ist, vgl. *hywb* Acts 25:15C² CCPA IIB oder *hywb'* 2Cor 3:9T^b CCPA IIB.

עיני 'watch' [S. 633]: Hinzufügen ist Ma'lūla *'ayni*, das das Verb noch heute gebraucht, Arnold 1990, 180 f.

עמי 'darkness' [S. 643]: Die Wurzel scheint eher gemeinaram. zu sein, denn sie ist bezeugt für das Syr., TA, SA und nun auch das Mand., vgl. *dhk' rwhyh d-dyw' kd gwmrt' d-nwr' d-dhk' w'my' hkw't rwhyh* »The spirit of Dew was quenched like coal of fire which is quenched and becomes dim like the spirit« 1Ac84-86 (Ch. Müller-Kessler, 'A Charm against Demons of Time', in C. Wunsch [Hrsg.], *Mining the Archives. Festschrift for Christopher Walker on the Occasion of His 60th Birthday*, Dresden 2002, 187).

עסק 'matter, affair' [S. 649]: Diese Wurzel kann kaum von Targum Onqelos beeinflusst sein, da zahlreiche Belege für das

CPA vorliegen, siehe *l'rb* 'sqh »on account of his matter« Acts 25:16C² CCPA IIB.

עקד 'prostration' [S. 657]: Was soll ראה דיון in der bibliographischen CPA-Angabe bedeuten?

עקרב 'scorpion' [S. 660]: das Nomen ist fem., nicht mask. ערב: ערובה 'Shabbat eve' [S. 661]: Das CPA-Beispiel *l'rwbt* *dšwbt* bezeichnet eine Lektion des Kirchenjahres in dem Lektionar, die am Samstagabend vorgetragen wird; es handelt sich nicht um ein Zitat aus Rom 5:5C² CCPA IIB.

ערב 'bird' [S. 661]: CPA hat *l'rb* anstelle von *l'rb* Gn 8:7 Lewis 1897, als Fehllesung von Talšir [טלשיר] 1981 übernommen.

ערדען 'frog' [S. 663]: Hinzuzufügen ist Ma'lūla *wurta'na* Arnold 1990, 343.

ערע 'occurrence' [S. 664]: Hinzuzufügen ist QA לעורעהון לעורעה, Genesis Apokryphon XXI:31, XXII:13 und CPA ר' Schultheß 1903, 19. Das CPA zeigt konsequent wie das JPA die Dissimilation des ersten Gutturals /' / > /' /, das SA hingegen nur selten.

ערער 'mishap' [S. 665]: Das CPA-Beispiel *rr ty'wr* Dt 7:16 ist inkorrekt, da die Textstelle *ndd tynwd* Dt 7:26P^b CCPA I gelesen wird; vgl. die Variante *ndwd tndd* C³ CCPA I.

ערפט anstelle von ערפד [S. 666]: Es kann kaum ein Wechsel von /d/ > /t/ vorliegen; vielmehr liegt ein orthographisches Problem zugrunde, verursacht durch die Unsicherheit in dieser späten aram. Periode zwischen den verschiedenen Dentalen zu differenzieren.

ערק 'fleeing' [S. 666]: CPA hat *wytpš* anstelle von *wytpsy*.

עשק 'deprivation' [S. 668]: Die angeführte CPA-Stelle ist nicht aus Schultheß 1903 entnommen, sondern aus Lewis 1897.

עשש 'darkness' [S. 668]: Beim CPA korrigiere Dt 10:12 zu 10:22.

עתר 'richness' [S. 670]: CPA hat *tykwlyn* anstelle von *tykwlyn* Is 60:16 Lewis 1897.

פדע 'injure' [S. 673]: Auch im CPA belegt; siehe unter פדע.

פוס 'appeasement' [S. 676]: Es besteht kein Grund, eine derartige, nichtexistente künstliche Wurzel anzusetzen. Wenn überhaupt, dann wäre nur פיס möglich für griech. *πεῖσαι*. פרזל 'iron' [S. 701]: Es besteht kein Grund, Defektiv- und Pleneschreibung zu trennen und im gleichen Lemma zwei verschiedene Nominalabschnitte für ein und dasselbe Wort zu schaffen.

פרע¹ 'uncovering' [S. 706]: Hinzuzufügen ist CPA *wl' hw' šb' ypr' yth*. »he did not want to expose her« Mt 1:19C³ CCPA IIA (= Lewis 1909, 36).

פרע² 'pay, requital' [S. 707]: Es besteht keine Verbindung zu einem *pr'* im CPA, da Verb wie Nomen bereits durch Duensing 1906, 41, n. 1 zu *pd'* 'to wound' emendiert worden waren, dies auf der Basis der Identifizierung des Land-Fragments mit Cyr 6:34Pⁱ CCPA V.

צבע¹ 'finger' [S. 720]: Vgl. CPA *š:b'thwn* 'their fingers' Mk 23:4C¹ CCPA IIA und Ma'lūla *spa'ta* mit Fem.-Endung im Gegensatz zum SA und JPA, siehe A. Spitaler, *Grammatik des neuaramäischen Dialekts von Ma'lūla (Antilibanon)*, Leipzig 1938, 7.

צבע² 'moisture' [S. 721/2]: צבעה bedeutet 'dye' und nicht die Farbbezeichnung 'scarlet', welche im SA ועוריתה wäre, hier S. 223 inkorrekt wiedergegeben im Englischen als 'yarn' bzw. im Hebr. als השני; siehe dazu das Lexem זוהר.

צלצל 'bird' [S. 734]: Das Wort korreliert mit CPA *šršr'* 'a kind of locust', da die Phoneme /r/ und /l/ dialektbedingt

wechslern können; eine solche Bedeutung paßt besser in den Kontext von Dt 28:42 als eine Vogelbezeichnung.

קבל 'front, face' [S. 747]: 'face' ist kaum die Grundbedeutung von קבל.

קובע 'head-cover' [S. 761]: Das Wort muß nicht aus Targum Onqelos stammen, da es auch im CPA gebraucht wird, *qwb*: *yhwn* 'their capitals' in Ex 26:32V CCPA I (= Duensing 1906). Warum nicht unter der Wurzel קבע?

קלי 'roasting' [S. 778]: Vgl. und lies jetzt die CPA-Textpassage *gly'n pr: yn* 'roasting bran' Epistle of Jeremia 42, inkorrekt gelesen in CCPA I.

קסם 'witchcraft' [S. 788]: קסם bedeutet 'to divine, predict from an oracle' und nicht 'to perform magic', für das חרש gebraucht wird, im Hebr. כשף, vgl. CPA *lhlyn dmgmr: yn l qsm: yhwn dšlm: y'* »concerning these who study the predictions of the idols« Cyr 4:37Pⁱ CCPA V; *'pymnyds hw' šymh qswm mn qryt'* »Epimenides was the name of a diviner from Crete« Ti 1:120 Zusatz CCPA IIB (= Gwilliam 1893, 20).

Beide Bedeutungen sollten strikt auseinandergelassen werden, da im Alten Orient primär zwei verschiedene Berufe damit erfaßt sind; vgl. auch נחש. Übersetze הלא לא נחש ביעקב הלא לא נחש ביעקב »there is no sorcery in Jacob, no divination in Israel« anstelle von »there is no divination in Jacob, no witchcraft in Israel«; siehe dazu allgemein B. Pongratz-Leisten, *Herrschaftswissen in Mesopotamien* (SAAS X; Helsinki 1999). Die korrekte CPA-Wurzel ist *qsm*, nicht *qsm*; letzteres stammt aus einer späten Handschrift, in der die Sibyllen teilweise nicht mehr differenziert werden; dazu Müller-Kessler 1991, 46-47. Wenn *qsm* und *nhš* identisch wären, müßten sie in der aram. magischen Literatur auch vorhanden und austauschbar sein, was nicht der Fall ist. *qsm* ist in dieser spezifischen Textgattung gar nicht belegt.

קסטר 'lead' [S. 788]: Lies im CPA *wqy[s]tr' w'[ybr]* »and tin and lead« entsprechend dem originalen Ez 22:20 CCPA I. Im CPA liegt die Bedeutung 'tin' vor, nicht 'lead', wie auch in dem JPA-Beispiel כסטרטא aus Targum Neofiti, doch scheint SA Ex 15:10 es als 'lead' zu verstehen.

רבע¹ 'lying down' [S. 812]: מרבע 'to mate' sollte unter Af. eingeordnet werden, da למרבע ein Inf. Af. ist und zu trennen ist von den Varianten des Inf. Pe. למרבע. Ebenso gebraucht das CPA dieses Verb in beiden Stämmen.

רגג 'affection' [S. 815]: Auch das CPA kennt diese Wurzel, aber im abstrakten Plur. tant., *r: ygw'n* 'desire' Ti 3:3T^d CCPA IIB (= Lewis 1900, 66).

רוי¹ 'secret' [S. 826]: Die Ansetzung von Wurzeln nach ihrer nominalen Bedeutung führt zu Problemen, wie sie dieses Lemma רוי zeigt. Die Wurzel רוי ist denominiert aus Iranischem *raz* = רז 'secret', doch verwendet das SA dieses Verb in einer sekundären Bedeutung רוי 'to comprehend'. Ein Vergleich mit dem JPA and CPA ist insofern überflüssig, als beide nur das Nomen kennen.

ריח 'fragrance' [S. 832]: Vgl. den identischen Gebrauch im CPA *qygr zprw' n' mryh* »but the stench I smell« Iob 6:7C³ CCPA I.

רכב¹ 'coupling, grafting' [S. 833]: Die Grundbedeutung der Wurzel ist 'to ride, mount', während 'to couple, graft' nur euphemistisch und sekundär anzusetzen ist. Wenn man רכב als kollektives 'chariotry' auffassen möchte, sollte dies auch in der Übersetzung zum Ausdruck kommen; der SA-Text hat jedenfalls nicht 'both chariots'.

Das Beispiel unter מרכב 'saddle' [S. 834], מרכבה או ירכב gehört unter das fem. Lemma מרכבה, das es sich bei dem Textbeispiel um einen Status absolutus

fem. handelt, der immer nach dem Indefinitpronomen כל folgen sollte. Nur wenn das folgende Nomen durch ein Demonstrativpronomen, Possessivpronomen, einer Genetivkonstruktion oder nachfolgenden Relativsatz determiniert ist oder übergeordnet ist, kann der Status emphaticus nach כל stehen. Auch die Tatsache, daß im SA teilweise falsche Beispiele in korrupten Handschriften auftreten, ändert daran nichts.

²רכב 'knee' [S. 834]: die Variante ארכובין sind entweder fixierte Duale oder Pluralformen, aber nicht Plur. tant. Sie sollten trotz divergierender Schreibung unter einem Lemma erscheinen.

²רסה 'healing' [S. 841]: Wie soll der Leser die folgende Eintragung verstehen: »שיכול ההגאים ע"י שיכול ההגאים« (by metathesis) embalmers רוקפין ישראל [רוחטן]. Was der Autor wohl meint, ist, daß das nicht weiter ergänzte [רוחטן] hier als Metathesis [רוחטן] begegnet, anstelle von *רוחטן[טין], doch müßte der Leser erst einmal diese Ergänzung selbst vornehmen. Der Eintrag wäre nur unter הנט sinnvoll, wo er aber überhaupt nicht erscheint und kein »embalmer /qattāl/ הנט or הנט« vorhanden ist.

רקן 'emptiness' [S. 850]: Das Lemma ist hochgradig künstlich angesetzt, da eine solche Wurzel im Westaram. nicht existiert. Es handelt sich um eine sekundäre Wurzel von רוק 'to be empty', augmentiert mit -n, die entweder unter der originären Wurzel רוק, oder unter der Sekundärwurzel רוקן angeführt werden sollte. Es ist zu bezweifeln, daß tatsächlich eine aramaisierte Form des hebr. ריקם (korrigiere im Englischen Segal 120 zu 50) vorliegt, da auch das Vorkommen von einer analogen Bildung *swħn* im CPA erklärt werden müßte.

רקע 'garment' [S. 851]: Die bessere CPA-Variante zeigt *bmr: q'n* Lk 2:7P^s CCPA IIA. Bei der Unform *bmrq'yt* liegt ein Fehlzitat vor. Belegt ist diese Passage nur spät als *bmrq'yn* BC und *bmrwq'nyt* A. Ohne exakte Quellenangaben ist der Benutzer des Wörterbuches hier verloren.

רקק 'spitting' [S. 852]: Hinzuzufügen ist CPA Pe. *rqq* in *bkn r: qw b'p: wy* »then they spat into his face« Mt 26:67P^d CCPA IIA.

שבב 'neighbourhood' [S. 862]: Es liegt kein spezieller Einfluß des Targum Onqelos bzw. des Ostaram. vor, sondern ein gut bekanntes akkad. Lehnwort, das in einer Reihe von aram. Dialekten belegt ist, so auch in Ma'lūla als *šbabō* 'neighbour' Bergsträsser 1921, 88, nicht berücksichtigt bei Kaufman 1974, 101, sowie im SLBA auch in dem magischen Text D. Levene, »and by the name of Jesus...«, *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 6, 1999, 286, 6 [dort nicht erkannt].

שבעתי 'seven' [S. 866]: Nicht adjektivisch, sondern eine Zahl im Stat. constr. wie bei חמשיתי 'fifty' S. 282, ארבעתי 'four' S. 813, אשתתי 'six' S. 938.

שבררין 'rays of light' [S. 869]: Hier liegt kaum Targum Onqelos-Einfluß vor, das Wort ist eher gemeinaram., mit der Bedeutung '(day) blindness', belegt im babyl. Talmud als *šbr'ry* Gittin 69a, im Syr. als *šmrmr*, siehe Brockelmann 1928, 787, und im Mand. als Bezeichnung eines Krankheitsdämons, vgl. *šmbr'ry' zkry' wmn šmbryry' nwqb* [t'] »male and female nightblindness demons« BM 135791 III, 33-38 (unpubliziert). Ein Wurzelwörterbuch sollte es unter שבר listen. wird durch Reduplikation der Wurzel שבר und die erwartete Elision des ersten Radikals š im zweiten Bestandteil gebildet; dazu Brockelmann 1910, 367 f.; Epstein 1960, 112. Die im Syr. und Mand. erscheinende Wurzel שמר könnte die originäre sein, mit in einigen Dialekten vorhandener späterer Dissimilierung von *m > b*. Zur Wiedergabe als 'nightblindness' siehe M. Stol, 'Blindness and Night-Blindness in Akkadian', *Journal of Near Eastern Studies* 45, 1986, 297.

שעבד 'enslavement' [S. 916]: Eine analoge Šaf.-Bildung, die gemeinaram. ist.

שק 'thigh' [S. 925]: Vgl. CPA mit der Fem.-Endung *šqw:t* 'thighs' Jer 38 (31):19T CCPA I.

ש(א)קי 'brook, canal' [S. 925]: Vgl. CPA *šqy* 'brook' Jer 38(31):9T CCPA I (= Lewis 1900, 20).

²שקף 'watching' [S. 928]: Es handelt sich um keine aram. Wurzel, die ebenfalls nicht mit שקוף 'lintel' verwandt ist. שקוף ist aus dem Hebr. שקוף gebildet.

תאר 'image, form' [S. 939]: Im Gegensatz zum SA bildet das CPA die Wurzel bereits entsprechend dem Paradigma der *Πw*-Verba, in der leicht differierenden Bedeutung 'to understand'; trotz der wechselnden Schreibung ist im SA keine Aufspaltung zu תאר und תור S. 945 notwendig.

תוש 'whisper' [S. 946]: Welches Buch ist mit 'Land 149' gemeint? Es kann sich jedenfalls nicht um das in der Abkürzungsliste erwähnte Werk handeln, sondern um eines der weiteren Bände mit rein syrischen Texten.

תיש 'he-goat' [S. 948]: 'goat' ist der Terminus für das weibliche Tier.

תכלה 'purple' [S. 949]: Unter dem Lemma ארגון [S. 59] ist תכלה als 'blue' übersetzt, hier jedoch 'purple'.

תמר 'palm' [S. 956]: Das zutreffende Lemma ist תמרה wie bei תאנה 'fig', da der Sing. emph. תמרתה lautet, doch im Plur. eine Mask.-Endung תמרין zeigt; vgl. zum SA Macuch 1982, 276, zum Syr. Nöldeke 1898, 53, Brockelmann 1928, 828. In den neuwestaram. Dialekten wird es als *nomen unitatis* behandelt, vgl. Sing. *cam^rta*, Plur. *čamra* Arnold 1990, 296. Bereits Nöldeke 1875, 173 notierte die fem. Formen für das Syr, im Sing. *tmrt* Land Anecd. II, 106 bzw. babyl. Talmud תומרתה Sota 49a; die wird nun gestützt durch QA Sing. abs. תמרא Genesis Apocryphon XIX,14; Sing. emph. תמרתה Genesis Apocryphon XIX, 15, 16. Die *qutl*-Form < *qat*l תומרין scheint die bessere Variante zu sein, da auch das CPA *twmr: yn* aufweist, siehe FMSD 17b:13 CCPA III.

תנה 'rest' [S. 956]: תנה basiert nicht auf einem *ethpeel*, sondern ist eine sekundäre Wurzel von נוה; vgl. für das Mand. und SA Nöldeke 1875, 84, der bereits auf den Gebrauch im SA hinweist. Es ist hier als Ittaf. wie im Ostaram. zu analysieren, nicht als Pa.; siehe Ch. Müller-Kessler, 'Phraseology in Mandaic Incantations and its Rendering in Various Eastern Aramaic Dialects. A Collection of Magic Terminology', *Aram* 11-12 (1999-2000), 306.

תרין 'two' [S. 963/4]: Die Ordinalzahl תנין ist ein von der Wurzel TNY abgeleitetes Adjektiv und sollte auch unter dieser aufgeführt werden.

Jena, Dezember 2002

Christa MÜLLER-KESSLER

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BÖHM, M. — Samarien und die Samaritai bei Lukas. (Wissenschaftliche Untersuchungen zum Neuen Testament 2. Reihe 111) J.C.B. Mohr (Paul Siebeck) Verlag, Tübingen, 1999. (23 cm, XIV, 367). ISBN 3-16-147255-1. DM 118,-

Böhm's book is an interesting achievement. It has to be admitted that its quality was under-estimated by this reviewer at first glance: only on careful examination did I realise the ambitiousness of the task she had set for herself

in her determination to get to a definite and ironclad conclusion, without in any way bringing in guesswork as a prop. In fact, her repeated mention of a passage in Matthew that seemed incompatible with her overall picture of Jesus's policy reminded me of Darwin's habit of keeping a section in his notebook to remind himself of data not yet reconciled with his formulation of theory. This caution is taken too far at times, specially in her omission of undated Samaritan theologoumena. Such sources can be dated within limits, and can be related to tendencies known to have existed in the New Testament period, if the primary Samaritan sources are known thoroughly and the relevant modern studies have been used. There is an inevitable overall impression that Böhm has not been in constant contact with colleagues familiar with the whole range of material, nor has she mastered it herself. Lest this remark be taken as unfairly severe — obviously there are practical limits on anyone's reading — it is enough to point out that Böhm treats Samaritan theology as if it had no internal divisions, and the Dositheans don't get a mention, to cite the most glaring instance.

The purpose of the book can be set out in a few words. Taking as a datum that Luke's Gospel and the Book of Acts as we have them in their final form are the work of one author, the questions to be answered are, first, whether the references to Samaritans and people living in Samaria always refer to the same community; second, whether Israelites or heathens are envisaged in each place; third, how the author of Luke — Acts saw these people; and fourth, how they were seen by Jesus and the Apostles. I have departed from Böhm's own terminology, which, although common amongst New Testament scholars and endemic amongst theologians, is cumbersome because inaccurate. Böhm's terms "Judentum" and "Heidentum" express a false dichotomy. She knows this herself, and over and over says that a community are not "Jews", but then actually they are "Jews", because they are "true to the worship of YHWH", but then again they are not "Jews" because they "don't recognise the status of Jerusalem". At times, the entanglement makes it very hard to work out *precisely* how the possibilities are assessed by her. The difference is of course between "die Religion Israels" and "Heidentum", as the author occasionally lets on. The question is then whether the particular inhabitants of Samaria mentioned in each case are Israelites that are not Jews, i.e. the community called "Samaritans" by outsiders, or whether they are non-Israelites. No scholar in the Samaritan field would have fallen into such a trap: though it is really only a variant on the habit of theologians of talking about "the Exodus of the Jews from Egypt" or "the Jewish prophets", or, worst of all, "the Jewish Law". For the readers of this journal, it would be an unnecessary annoyance to sort out what is wrong with all this usage: enough to point out that the Jewish liturgy does not use the term "Jews" and the Samaritan liturgy does not use the term "Samaritans". When, therefore, the question is whether there might be some theological disagreement over and beyond the question of the true site of the Deuteronomic sacred place, and this disagreement shows up between Jewish groups, as well as between Samaritans and Jews, the reader is given an unnecessarily difficult task, sometimes an impossible one. Having said all this, however, I stress that the quality of the argument underlying the cumbersome wording is consistently outstanding.

The answer to the main question, according to Böhm, is that in every case, or at least in every case where the identi-

fication matters, the individual is what we would call "a Samaritan" and the community is the community of the Samaritans, so that the mission to Samaria by Philip and others was a mission to the Samaritans. The corollary is that neither Jesus nor the Apostles saw any inconsistency between being a Samaritan and being an Israelite. Now, it is true that this is the conclusion that will be arrived at both intuitively and logically by any reader familiar with the issues. Nevertheless, the systematic elimination of any other possibility has enormous value. The most obvious is that one prevalent source of confusion can be eliminated from New Testament scholarship and banished from commentaries on the New Testament. Also, much of the documentary material from the period can now be assessed more sharply and accurately. This second point is more important than might be immediately apparent. If Böhm's studies of the background documents are re-read in the light of her conclusions, they become a valuable anthology with a considerable amount of original comment. In some cases, notably the polemical passage II Kings XVII: 24-41 (a very late interpolation inconsistent with other passages in the book), she has contributed substantially to the questions of motivation and origin. In regard to Christian theology, there is a lot that can be inferred about the lines of thought that enabled Christians of Jewish origin to agree with Christians of Samaritan origin in the desacralisation of both erstwhile sacred places, the site of the Jerusalem Temple and Mt. Gerizim. One way of expressing the process would be to say that the only way to resolve the ancient dispute was to *dissolve* it. The Epistle to the Hebrews, following Jesus's own lead in John IV, does this by putting new emphasis on the ancient concept of the Heavenly Tabernacle. Now, Böhm does not go into this question and its resolution in detail in her exposition, but it turns up more or less implicitly or explicitly in several places and is explicit (though not developed) amongst her concluding Nine Theses.

Lack of familiarity with modern studies and the primary Samaritan sources was mentioned above. One particular case is likely to cause serious confusion to the readers for whom the book is intended. In several places Böhm raises the question of whether there was ever a stone temple on Mt. Gerizim, as opposed to some kind of sacred enclosure. Her tentative assessment is that there is not much evidence for a sacred stone structure (though of course stone buildings for practical purposes were needed). Her survey of the archaeological evidence is very thorough, but these observations should have been accompanied by a reference to the place where Abu'l-Fath. opposes the false structure built by Eli to the true sacred enclosure on Mt. Gerizim. Now, Böhm, along with Zangenberg, can be excused for not knowing Arabic, but what is not excusable is not using the Latin translation of the corresponding passage in what is called the Arabic Book of Joshua and the accompanying explicit clarification of the author's terminology by Juynboll (T.G.J. Juynboll, *Chronicon Samaritanum Arabice conscriptum cui titulus est Liber Josuae*, Leiden 1848; there are explicit notes on pp.306-307, p.239 and p.261. His earlier book *Commentarii in Historiam Gentis Samaritanae*, Leiden 1846, pp.89-90 is presupposed by Juynboll in his notes to the chronicle here). In the original, the false structure is called a *naos* (not a normal Arabic word, and clearly chosen for precision) and the true enclosure is called a *haykal* (which means a framework in Arabic, though Christian usage applies it under the influence of Syriac to the

Jerusalem Temple). There can be no doubt as to the meaning intended by the use of the term *haykal* here because the Arabic Book of Joshua, in another place, i.e. the start of ch. XLII, says that this *haykal* could be taken apart and carried (by one man!), and was packed away in a cave at the end of the Time of Favour. Böhm does refer (p.73) to another place where Abu 'l-Fath. uses the term *haykal* on its own (72:9 in Vilmar's edition of the Arabic), but this passage is less easy to interpret, because it is not concerned with the contrast between a building and the framework or curtains of the Tabernacle. Böhm uses a German translation (by Jürgen Zangenberg) of an inadequate English translation by Paul Stenhouse. Zangenberg, followed by Böhm, misses the point by not being familiar with the work of Juynboll. The result is that Böhm actually seems to believe (following Zangenberg's lead) that there is a Samaritan tradition that accepted a stone building in place of the Tabernacle, and that this tradition is documented! Unfortunately, others will be misled by this claim.

Two other instances of error due to neglect of material will be enough.

On p.78 Böhm correctly points out that Judaism was very varied in the New Testament period. When she then says that the Sadducees only accepted the Pentateuch as Scripture, she gives no evidence from historical sources for this startling claim, which, if it were true, would surely have been mentioned in the Rabbinic sources. There is a reference to a book by Johann Maier, who in turn (though Böhm does not specify this) purportedly derives the information from Josephus (Antiquities XIII: 297-298, Loeb vol. 7 p.376). What Maier really relies on is, however, not Josephus, but a misreading of the passage out of context by Origen followed uncritically as usual by Epiphanius. Josephus actually says that the Sadducees insisted that entirely new laws invented and then handed down by the Pharisees had no validity, and that only the laws of Moses (*along with their traditional observances*) had validity. Compare Antiquities XVIII:12 and 16, which confirms what is implied by the context of the previous passage. See in detail my article *L'Antiquité des Racines du Karaïsme*, JEOL, 1997, pp.101-116, and specially section 3.

Nowhere does Böhm mention the internal dispute among the Samaritans as to whether the mountain is holy in itself, or only holy when the Tabernacle is present. She is of course familiar with the term "the Restorer" but has not connected the acceptance of this figure with the debate over the status of the mountain. The reconciliation of the two views is later than the New Testament period and can justifiably be ignored, but the original dispute is ancient. The relevant sources on the Dositheans, who took the view that the mountain had no holiness without the Tabernacle, are extensively cited in the secondary literature, and are well known.

In spite of these criticisms, Böhm's book is an impressive example of the integration of disparate material into a compelling argument. The scope of the book is very ambitious, and the ambition has been realised.

Balaclava (Melbourne), January 2003

I.R.M. BÓID

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NIESSEN, Fr. — Eine samaritanische Version des Buches Yehošua^c und die Šobak-Erzählung. (Texte und Studien zur Orientalistik 12). Georg Olms Verlag GmbH, Hildesheim, 2000. (21 cm, VIII, 466). ISBN 3-487-11060-1; ISSN 0176-0041. DM 98,-.

Niessen's edition and study of this previously unpublished text will help greatly in the longstanding (and so far inconclusive) task of disentangling the strands of the Samaritan historical traditions, and in assessing their historicity. As this segment of text corresponds to the events of the book of Joshua of the Old Testament, most parts of which would fit under one definition or another of the term "fiction", the question of the historicity of the Samaritan traditions does not arise directly, but certainly the question of their antiquity and independence does arise; and so there is some bearing on the question of the historicity and independence of the Samaritan traditions corresponding to the books of Samuel — Kings, Chronicles — Ezra-Nehemiah, and Maccabees, in which the fictional component is offset by historical fact, increasing as time goes on, but not quite complete even in I Maccabees. *This review has been extended to the length of an article so as to move Niessen's book and related publications into the domain of Old Testament studies.* It remains true that the use of the Samaritan historical tradition is not easy, mainly because of the way it has been transmitted. To the Samaritans, such records are not sacred books, though they are assigned considerable respect. There is accordingly an enormous task to be done just in sorting out the various divisions of the lines of transmission. Also, there is always the concern that the Samaritan tradition might only be a late construct, produced for polemical purposes. This review is not the place to go into these questions in detail, but something needs to be said here so as to show Old Testament scholars that it is methodologically unsound to ignore the tradition altogether by relegating it to the domain of scholars of the Hellenistic period, or the Byzantine period. On the question of the antiquity of the tradition, there are the following general considerations.

First, the core datum of the tradition is that the sacred place in the time of Joshua was on Mt. Gerizim (or in one Dosithean variant, on the flat ground opposite the mountain, where Jacob had his vision of the union of heaven and earth). This sanctuary was called Bethel. The sanctuary set up by Eli was therefore a counterfeit, and the later sanctuary in Jerusalem was no more than the outcome of the original harm done by Eli. After the Mosaic Tabernacle was deserted by the divine presence, due to general apostasy represented by Eli's sanctuary but much more widespread, the High Priest °ZY (°Azzi, Masoretic °Uzzi) hid the Tabernacle, which was made unfindable by divine intervention. The two sanctuaries set up by Jeroboam were explicable as a clumsy attempt to remedy the damage, but the cult was contaminated. A righteous remnant, a minority even in the north, continued the legitimate cult in the true location, where there was never a stone temple building. Now this core datum, and all that follows from it, is not a late invention, but a more emphatic statement of an attitude that is well attested in what is called the Old Testament, but more obliquely, and with acceptance of both the southern and the northern sanctuary. (a) The Pentateuch does not specify where the single Deuteronomic sacred place is to be. (b) The Pentateuch does, however, give prominence to sites that are near Mt. Gerizim (the Samaritans would say that

they are actually on the mountain) in connection with the Patriarchs, and in other ways. (c) Jerusalem is not mentioned in the Pentateuch. (d) Not even Jewish apologetics identifies Moriah with Jerusalem till the books of Chronicles. (e) There are multiple versions of the order of events of the book of Joshua, some of which indicate a location for the main sanctuary in an area near Shechem. (f) The first book of Samuel does not say a word about where the sanctuary was before Shilo. (g) Although the evidence is scattered, it seems that Eli was descended from Ithamar, not Phineas, and was therefore not a legitimate High Priest. But 'Uzzi was certainly descended from Phineas. How could Eli take the Ark into battle, if it was the real one, without the disapproval of the Deuteronomic editor? If Shilo had been the true location, how could any fault of its priests end its potential status? But Jerusalem would not have been chosen unless Shilo had been disqualified. (h) The Ark and tent just fade out of the picture after Solomon's death. The legendary explanation of how it was that the Babylonians did not capture the Ark have no support, and surely a vague reference to it being hidden somewhere would be appropriate, unless it never was in the Jerusalem Temple. If it says in Jeremiah III: 16 that the Ark will not be needed as a focus of pious attention in the ideal future, then it must have been regarded as only a symbolic or memorial copy of the Mosaic original. What else can WL' YPQDW or the Greek *oude episkephthêsetai* imply without anachronistic antinomianism? (i) Nothing is said about what happened to the Mosaic Tabernacle after the crossing of the Jordan except in Chronicles (I Chronicles XXI: 29). Besides, the Pentateuch does not command the building of a stone temple building (as Stephen pointed out to his cost) and Nathan focuses on a metaphorical house. His obscure words about a tent are at best not encouraging. (j) The choice of Jerusalem is nowhere legitimated by a prophetic announcement, not even by Nathan if you read carefully. Notice that the Babylonian Talmud, Zevah.im 54b, gives a fanciful explanation of the choice of location, and that the question is otherwise avoided in Rabbinic texts. The argument from I Chronicles XXII: 1 is not used, perhaps because of its flimsiness. The quotation of II Chronicles VII: 7 in Zevah.im 59ab has a wording of the verse that suggests that Solomon felt free to depart from what Moses had ordained by re-designing the sanctuary; and see also Mechilta Bah.odesh XI on Exodus XX: 21. The reading of MT of Chronicles here looks like a euphemism. (k) Jeroboam's breakaway is recognised by both Kings and Chronicles as having divine approval, and neither book at this point expresses disapproval of the two locations, only the form of the observances at Bethel (which one?) and Dan. Hosea does not say that Bethel (which one?) is illegitimate in itself. Neither does any other prophet, and several had occasion or opportunity to do so, if they had wanted to, in reference to Bethel or other northern sanctuaries. How could Rehoboam have gone to Shechem for his coronation unless he (and the Jerusalem prophets) recognised that there was a sacred place nearby that could not be ignored, no matter what? (l) When Josiah destroyed the sanctuary at Bethel, he did not destroy the sacred altar (and note the Targum to I Kings XIII: 2). He defiled it, to make it unusable for a long while. On the other hand, he did destroy the altar nearby, built by Jeroboam. (m) There are bits of the liturgy of a northern sanctuary in the Old Testament, the longest pieces being some of the Psalms. (Psalm LXXX is incontestable). If Hosea XII: 3b, 4 to 6, is read in the MT, the Greek, and the Targum, it will be seen

that the variations in tense and pronouns are due to the realisation that it is from a piece of liturgy re-actualising Jacob's experience at Bethel with the experience of the worshippers at the sacred place. The previous verses may well be a paraphrase of a set prologue inviting self-examination.

The second general consideration in regard to the antiquity of the Samaritan tradition is that the Samaritan community is certainly no later in its origin than the start of the Greek period, and evidence for its existence in the Persian period is very strong. Regardless of the historicity of the Samaritan claim to be the direct spiritual descendants of those that resisted the apostasy of Eli, they are certainly the descendants of those that resisted the claims of Jerusalem over the whole of what is called Old Testament history.

The third general consideration is that the books of Joshua, Judges, and Samuel are so late and have so many variant forms (not forgetting Josephus) that it would be difficult to separate the Samaritan tradition from the mixture. There is much in it that could have no polemical purpose and is related to one or other of the known recensions of these books.

The fourth general consideration is that the various recensions of the Samaritan tradition do not contradict each other, except in minor matters, and even then, not often. The various recensions differ in what events are put in or left out, and the amount and choice of detail.

There is, finally, a consideration that applies specially to the Samaritan book of Joshua. It is methodologically easy to compare this detailed narrative with the other known forms of Joshua — Judges, and it is surprising how informative these comparisons are. Niessen has gone a long way with this task.

There are several recensions of the Samaritan book of Joshua (actually Joshua — Judges). This book is loosely attached to a longer history in many of the text-witnesses, but it has its own identity. The book is attested in Hebrew and Arabic. In a forthcoming article, I quote an explicit statement from one recension of the Arabic saying that the Arabic was relatively recently translated from Hebrew, but that the Hebrew was translated from Aramaic. Whether any known form of the Hebrew is the one translated directly from Aramaic is not known, but Niessen's work leads me to wonder whether this might be it, or at least, a revised metrical riming form of it. The Aramaic has not survived. It seems that the original Hebrew from which the Aramaic version was translated has not survived, but then again, would a Hebrew text known to be original ever have been abandoned, i.e. was the Aramaic the original form? As there is nothing in the wording or content of the book to make it specifically Samaritan, and as it is supported in its arrangement of material by one or other witness, and as it finishes before the apostasy of Eli, and as it has its own identity even within the longer history, it would be methodologically sound to examine the possibility of it being neither Samaritan nor Jewish in origin, but another survivor of the multiple recensions of the book of Joshua of the first century B.C. or thereabouts that are already known — MT, more than one form from Qumran, two forms in Greek translation, another one known to Josephus, and one more (at least) lying behind some allusions in Rabbinic sources (e.g. Sifrei on Deuteronomy XI: 29-30 or Midrash Tanna'im on XI: 29), and readings in the Old Latin differing from either of the two surviving Greek texts.

The book of Joshua is known in at least two recensions in Hebrew. The text used by Niessen belongs to a recension that

has come down to us attached to a longer history. This recension has two forms, differing greatly in the type of Hebrew used. Using the terminology of Form A for the form used by Niessen and Form B for the other, it can be said that Form B of this longer history is well known, as large parts of it have been published and the mss. are numerous; whereas mss. of Form A are rare, and only a small part has been published. The sections of Form B corresponding to Joshua – Judges – Samuel – Kings were published, not at all accurately, by John Macdonald in 1969 as *The Samaritan Chronicle No. II (or: Sepher Ha-Yamim). From Joshua to Nebuchadnezzar* (Berlin, Walter de Gruyter = BZAW 107). A later part of this recension, covering the religious and cultural renaissance starting in the late 3rd century A.D., was published in both text-forms in 1981 by J.M. Cohen as *A Samaritan Chronicle etc.* (Leiden, E.J. Brill). Previously, only a small section of Form A, on the death of Moses, had been published, first by Gaster, and later by Niessen as his M.A. thesis. The question of the relationship between Form A and Form B is very important, because it must be addressed before the chronicle can be used by Old Testament scholars. Macdonald's main argument for the priority of Form B is based on unbelievable carelessness. He observed, correctly, that the date at the end of one ms. was written out *in words* as 1026 A.H. (= 1616 A.D.). He observed, equally correctly, that all other mss. of Form B were modern, as was the one known ms. of Form A. Macdonald observed that the name of the scribe was Ghazâl bin Khiḏr, a modern scholar, but thought this must be some other person of the same name. Now, the scribe would be known from genealogies and from other mss. if he had been working in 1616. Macdonald did not notice that the handwriting was exactly the same as that of the modern scholar, even though he was familiar with numerous mss. by this person. Nor did he notice that the end of the ms. (in the same handwriting, and not in an appendix) mentions events of the late 19th and early 20th century! It follows that the hundreds have been left out, and that the date should be 1326 A.H. (1908 A.D.), at the height of this scholar's activity. Ben-H.ayyim has pointed out more than once that a ms. written out in 1616 A.D. would not mention events of the early 20th century in the body of the text in the original handwriting. Nor would the same scribe mention the person that was High Priest before the First World War, Ya^cqûb bin Hârûn. It can be seen why Macdonald says in several of his publications that Samaritan handwriting has not changed over the centuries. Unfortunately, very many scholars have continued to refer to this matter of dating as if it were a mere matter of opinion, without having taken in the evidence of the content of the ms., because they have not read (or can't read) Ben-H.ayyim's articles written in Hebrew. Niessen, who has certainly read the material, makes the same mistake, but in this case the oversight can be ascribed to pressure of time, since this book was his doctoral thesis, and perhaps he had not yet learnt that statements in standard reference works are not always based on examination of the evidence. One does, however, see signs of hastiness in his dismissal of Gaster's text of Joshua, uncritically following Yellin and Yahuda (pp. 8-9), while on p. 14 describing the very same mss., in Crown's edition, as important, without seeing the connection. These two mss. are quoted in the notes. Gaster's edition has therefore not been read; or Crown's detailed introduction either. The main merit of the book is not, however, to be looked for in the introduction, but in the impressively accurate translation and notes. *The linguistic notes (along with*

their summary in the introduction) are the most detailed ever assembled on the question of dating the two types of Hebrew. Niessen has proven that the Hebrew is not modern, but on the other hand the influence of Arabic can be seen. My own impression is that the exercise of writing in Hebrew, not Arabic, and without an excessive admixture of Aramaic, sets the text at the time of the revival of the 14th century — but I would not have dared to be so definite without Niessen's evidence. Nevertheless, why is the well-known Arabic form of Niessen's text not used at all to clarify obscurities in the Hebrew? (Macdonald p. 12; many mss.).

The notes on the relationship between the text edited and other forms of the book of Joshua are consistently accurate and thorough. So as to make the work more accessible, I list here a few observations and corrections. The list is as complete as I could make it, and is still not very long.

- (a) The listing of the mss. on p.14 is not entirely accurate. Gaster 1142 is 375 in the current listing, not 257; and note that Niessen has previously said that Gaster 863 is no. 257, correctly.
- (b) Niessen says that the ms. edited is the only ms. of this text. Not so. It is the only such ms. in the John Rylands Library. Niessen has not mentioned any mss. of the relevant texts, the book of Joshua and related Hebrew texts, outside the John Rylands Library. Within the constraints of time in preparing a doctoral thesis, this omission is forgivable, but at some stage Niessen will have to look at the relevant mss. in Girton College Library at Cambridge, the Jewish National and University Library in Jerusalem, the French National Library in Paris, the High Priest's Library near Nablus (the Freie Universität Berlin has microfilms), the British Library (which acquired a lot of the Gaster mss.; they are not all in Manchester, contrary to common belief); the Jewish Theological Seminary in New York; Dropsie College Library in Philadelphia; the Prussian State Library in Berlin; and a few others. My notes indicate that there is at least one other ms. of this text, and if I am able to trace the references, I will publish the information.
- (c) 15b: 8 of the text, with its note. The statement that II Corinthians III: 13 has a negative evaluation of the veil over Moses's face alludes to an error whereby Paul's argument is not read properly and the verse is read out of context. Paul does not say that Moses's face was veiled so that the people would not realise the inadequacy of the Torah: he said that if the Torah, which was destined to be followed by something greater, was so holy that the people couldn't bear to see its reflection, then what followed is even greater in degree and kind. This error is common and is constantly being corrected, e.g. by the New Oxford Annotated Bible, notes *ad loc.*
- (d) 18a: 10 of the text, with its note. The word *shmh* is a noun, not a verb. The syntactic usage of the preposition seems to have been missed. The translation is correct.
- (e) 18b: 10. The meaning assigned in the note to the Arabic word *biqâc* is Andalusian, not Syrian. The word, if Arabic, means valleys. But it would be a lot simpler to treat the word in the text, *bq^c*, as a previously unattested masculine form of the Hebrew word *bq^ch*, which is in fact what Niessen has done in the translation.
- (f) 23b: 17. The words *kl spr* have been missed in the translation and commentary.

- (g) 27b: 19. Where is Rîf?
- (h) 28a: 26-27 has been correctly transcribed, but it should have been remarked that the ms. should have the letters *mn* in line 26, not line 27, and in line 27 should have *mn mn*. The translation is correct.
- (i) 32b: 9. Not quite “what happens” but rather “what is done”.
- (j) 36a: 1-2. The double mention of wild goats in the German translation is impossible. See the Rabbinic commentaries on Leviticus XI.
- (k) 36b: 27. Correct *mzbh*. To *mzrh*.
- (l) 37b: 10-11. The mention of Greater Armenia and Lesser Armenia is quite explicable and emendation is unnecessary. These two districts correspond to two districts of the Persian Empire, which included Armenia and Kurdistan. The “son of Yefet” is a Mede i.e. a Kurd, and his allies are all equally Iranian in the broad sense. The author of this piece of fiction has tried to avoid anachronism by not saying outright that he is talking about the Persian Empire, but Abu ‘l-Fath. is not so reticent about the identification when he introduces the story. The reference to Genesis X: 1 could have profitably been followed up. The story has therefore been framed from the viewpoint of the Byzantine Empire. It has long been recognised that this story is not an original part of the book.
- (m) 47b: 21-22. It needs to be added that if the text puts Joshua’s territories as all being not too far from Shechem, the final redaction must have been much later than the supposed events, let us say in the Hellenistic period. 25a: 9-10 are important for the history of composition and editing as well.

Finally, technical matters, perhaps beyond Niessen’s control. The Hebrew font used for the main text is not well chosen. On the coarse paper used, it is sometimes impossible, if the context gives no help, as in proper names, to distinguish *gimel* from *nun* or *resh* from *dalet* or *he* from *h.et* without looking up the photographic reproduction of the ms. at the end of the book. A much better font is used in the introduction and notes, but this, being smaller, is still not always clear. The Arabic font is too small and too flattened to be used on such paper. One wonders whether the title of the book is due to the publisher or the author. I don’t see why the Masoretic pronunciation is brought in. Either the normal German form, or the Samaritan form *Yê’ûsha* would have been appropriate. The profusion of unusual diacritical marks in the title, impossible to reproduce fully without special equipment, will not endear the publisher to librarians.

I have learnt a lot from Niessen’s careful editorial work. It is to be hoped that he will eventually publish more of this ms., as well as related texts, with the same thoroughness. He has already done enough to make it impossible for Old Testament scholars to ignore the Samaritan tradition. Although his work certainly has to be seen as building on and adding to previous studies, it is scientifically satisfactory (except for the neglect of the Arabic version, and the confusion over the Hebrew texts), thus removing the last excuse for avoiding the use of these texts. The excessive claims by Gaster and Macdonald for the originality and great antiquity of the extant Hebrew texts were easy to refute, and in the process the value of their content was overlooked. It is now time to investigate the question of whether the text edited by Niessen might be

the source of an Arabic version, rather than being a translation from Arabic; and if so, which Arabic version — or was there redactional work in the process of translation? How detailed is the Samaritan tradition overall, as compared to the other versions or forms of the book? I hope to be able to go into these questions, using as an example the passages corresponding to III: 13-17 of the MT, the drying up of the Jordan at a certain time of year and the way it was crossed on foot on this occasion, as well as a couple of other examples. If all the versions, (including Gaster’s), are compared, an old text similar to the one used by Josephus, but not the same, can be seen. Niessen has given us a valuable reference point for any such investigation.

Balaclava (Melbourne), January 2003

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PUMMER, Reinhard — Samaritan Marriage Contracts and Deeds of Divorce (Vol. II). Verlag Otto Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden, 1997. (30 cm, IX, 361, CXII pl.). ISBN 3-447-04010-6. DM 268,-.

Pummer has put an enormous amount of work into collecting all known Samaritan marriage and divorce documents. The main usefulness of the book is in the dated table of individuals and their relationships at the end of vol. II. This table is another important source of information for identifying named scribes or persons named by the scribe in Samaritan manuscripts. It is an essential reference for the specialist.

As this is the second volume, and it is years since the appearance of the first volume, there is no need to describe the method of presenting the material. The author deserves congratulation on having transcribed and published the whole relevant section of the Firkovitch collection in St. Petersburg, something that seemed unattainable when vol. I was prepared.

A valuable but seriously flawed appendage to the book is the translation (into somewhat fractured English) of all the introductory theological poems in these documents by Abraham Tal, along with linguistic and exegetical notes. Unfortunately, both the translation and the notes are unreliable.

Tal is familiar with the studies of Samaritan Hebrew that have been published, and his translation and notes are generally accurate, but the number of unnecessary errors is much too high, making a real trap for the unwary non-specialist. What follows is not a complete list, and does not include all the categories of error, but it will be enough to make the point that the errors could have been avoided if knowledgeable informants had been consulted now and then. (a) BL Or 12375c, line 6, and several times thereafter. The “Day of Horeb” is not the occasion of the theophany of the Burning Bush, but the day of the giving of the Torah. It is simply not true to say that Moses stepped into the fire of the Burning Bush: the quote from Marqé means that Moses stepped into the fire at the giving of the Torah. The word “day” as a name of an event means a *public* event. The word QWNH does not usually mean “owner” in Samaritan (or Jewish) liturgy, but either “maker” (if said of God) or “protagonist” (if said of a human). Moses was not the “owner” of the Day of Horeb. (b) Firkovitch X, 3, line 2, and very many times thereafter. The translation has “Merciful and gracious is his name. How

they multiplied and grew! (He) who in his highness has no associate, nor partner". The note says "Frequent formula of reverence and amazement. It generally occurs in connection with God's names and is probably related to their multitude (see Cowley, p.435, line 23; p.486, line 17)". The two references to Cowley's *Samaritan Liturgy* are mere padding. The two words RBW W^cS.MY are nouns, not verbs. The usage of MH that Tal has not understood can be heard in the *Jewish* liturgy. That they are nouns is clearly proven from the second reference to Cowley, which has the variant NYRWT MS^hBH.YM.....LMN RBW W^cS.MW L'LHY HS^hM HNKBD (and so on). In Firkovitch X, 4, line 2, the translation "How they multiplied and magnified" is not English. (c) Firkovitch X, 6, line 5, and frequently thereafter. The poet knows what he is doing when he says that the light referred to in Deuteronomy XXXIII: 2 comes from Moses and appears to people. The account of the giving of the Torah says over and over that the people did not see any clear light, but only what resembled volcanic activity; whereas we are told elsewhere that Moses's face shone with the light of the Torah. The light is certainly light from God, but through the medium of Moses. If the same passage from Deuteronomy says that this light radiated out over the world, then what is meant is not a murky glow. Tal's note here and elsewhere implying that the poet has transferred a divine quality to Moses shows exegetical insensitivity, as well as ignorance of the sources in the Samaritan liturgy and in Marqe. In the translation, for "he" read "which", the antecedent being the light, not Moses. (d) Firkovitch X, 14, line 7. For "(... so that from them) will arise (a chain of pure ones etc.)" read "would arise". The reference is to the purpose of a previous act, not a prediction. (e) Firkovitch X, 17, line 9, note. The verb YH.Z is from 'H.Z, not H.ZH, and the form is normal. (f) Firkovitch X, 23, line 12. It is not correct to say that the poet wrote "his dream" merely for the sake of the rime, instead of "the dream". Joseph had a dream, and it came true. Tal has not understood the verb WHFTRT, though he has correctly parsed it. (g) Firkovitch X, 26, line 4. The word B^cWDNW means "existent", not "in his position". The usage is normal in *Jewish* mediaeval Hebrew. Compare Genesis XLVIII: 15. (h) Firkovitch X, 30, line 3. For "And he wedded them in perfection" read "and they had a marriage in perfection", since the initial LHM can't be an object, and besides, the sequence of phrases shows that this was a resultant state, not the next event, since the marriage and its circumstance has already been mentioned. (i) Same line. It is just silly to say that the world was populated by Moses! The root of W'DYRT is not DWR, but HDR (j) Firkovitch X, 39, line 3. The translation "the living of the kings" is nonsense. While it is true that the text is partly obscured, there can be no doubt that HH.Y is a noun in the definite state, not the construct state; nor that the word after HMLK starts with H, not Y, and is another epithet. Read "the Living, the King, the Everlasting". (k) Firkovitch X, 42, line 6. It is impossible to say that the sea-creatures of the fifth day of creation are both heavenly and material beings. The correct reference is to the abyss before the first day of creation. See Cowley p.16 for the allusion. The translation "the gathering of the water" is off the track. The note to the effect that the parallel passage has DMYM is pointless, since the word is the same here. Anyway, the word DMYM means "of water", not "perfect". (l) Firkovitch X, 44, line 10. The translation "O that he would be seen there!"

is meaningless, as well as grammatically impossible. (m) Same line. For "And he singled out the tribe of Levi whom he put between his shoulders to dwell (there)", which is nonsense, read "And he singled out the tribe of Levi upon whose shoulders he laid a charge". The meaning is both metaphorical and literal. Contrary to Tal's note, the blessing of Benjamin has not been applied to Levi — and this is an appropriate occasion to say that if the translator thinks the poet has written something so silly, it is sure to be the translator that is wrong, here and elsewhere. (n) Firkovitch X, 46, lines 7 and 8. The total of the generations is ten and fifteen and then Moses and Aaron, not including Moses and Aaron. The preposition in the Hebrew is unambiguous. Tal's note shows that he does not know of the very common observation in *Jewish* and Samaritan texts that Moses is of the twenty-sixth generation, this number being the numerical value of the Divine Name. (o) Firkovitch X, 52, line 7. For "took" and "asked for" read "take" and "ask for". This is an admonition to the reader. (p) Firkovitch X: 53, line 7. It is impossible to say that BS^hDH HLBB means BLBB HS^hDH, or that "in the midst of the field" means "in the heart of the mountain". The phrase in the poem means, as in mediaeval *Jewish* Hebrew, "in the domain of the heart", as the following quotation makes clear. A knowledge of the range of meanings of the Arabic word *maydân* would have helped. (q) Firkovitch X: 42, line 8, and elsewhere. Jacob is the last person that could be described as "artless"! The meaning of the word TM is the same as in *Mediaeval Jewish Hebrew*, not its meaning in modern Israeli dictionaries. (r) Foreword, p.183. The phrase B^cLMH WB'H.RT means "in this world and the hereafter", not "in this world and the other world"; and Tal has confused the Arabic word 'âkhir with 'âkhar, and has quoted the Arabic adjective in the masculine instead of the feminine, not recognizing *dunyâ* as feminine, and not realizing that the noun understood, *dâr*, is feminine. Anyway, the second word would be WB'H.RYT in standard spelling.

There is no need for more examples.

Balaclava (Melbourne), January 2003

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